

DE CORPORE CHRISTI:
A MYSTICAL SERMON ON THE EUCHARIST
BY CONRAD OF SAINT GEORGE, O.CARM. (D. CA. 1310)*

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One of the great frustrations for the historian of the early Carmelites is the almost total lack of surviving documents from the first century of the Order's existence. We have Constitutions from 1281 and 1294, edited in the 1950s by Ludovico Saggi.¹ These early Constitutions include the *Rubrica prima*, the oldest written text produced by Carmelites about themselves, probably dating from the 1240s,² for centuries a core statement of Carmelite origin and identity

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¹ LUDOVICO SAGGI, ed., "Constitutiones capituli Londinensis anni 1281," *Analecta Ordinis Carmelitarum* 15 (1950): 205–45; LUDOVICO SAGGI, ed., "Constitutiones capituli Burdigalensis anni 1294," *Analecta Ordinis Carmelitarum* 18 (1953): 123–85; reprinted in *Corpus Constitutionum Ordinis Fratrum Beatissimae Virginis Mariae de Monte Carmelo*. Volume Primo, 1281–1456, ed. EDISON R.L. TINAMBUNAM and EMANUELE BOAGA, *Corpus Constitutionum Carmelitarum*, vol. 1 (Rome: Edizioni Carmelitane, 2011), 57–82, 83–117.

² There is now broad agreement that the *Rubrica prima* dates from the 1240s or a little earlier: LUDOVICO SAGGI, "Agiografia carmelitana," in *Santi del Carmelo: biografie da vari dizionari*, ed. Ludovico Saggi (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1972), 23–91; ADRIANUS STARING, *Medieval Carmelite Heritage: Early Reflections on the Nature of the Order*, *Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana*, vol. 16 (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1989), 33–37; CARLO CICONETTI, *La Regola del Carmelo: origine, natura, significato*, 2a ed. rivista e aggiornata, *Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana*, vol. 12 (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 2018), 180–187. In dissent RICHARD COPSEY, "Approaches to the Rule in the Early Centuries," in *The Carmelite Rule 1207–2007: Proceedings of the Lisieux Conference, 4–7 July 2005*, ed. Evaldo Xavier Gomes, et al., *Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana*, vol. 28 (Rome: Edizioni Carmelitane, 2008), 388–391, followed by PATRICK MULLINS, *The Carmelites and St Albert of Jerusalem: Origins and Identity*, *Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana*, vol. 38 (Rome: Edizioni Carmelitane, 2015), 57, have argued for a late date in the 1270s, but in my opinion have been convincingly refuted by Ciconetti, *ibid.*

and the ur-text of Carmelite attachment to the Prophet Elijah as the founder of the Order.³ A brief letter of the prior general Pierre de Millau to King Edward I of England dates from 1282.⁴ The anonymous chronicle *Universis Christifidelibus* is perhaps from 1289.⁵ However, the only substantial text by a named Carmelite author from the 13th century which has been known to date is the circular letter *Ignea sagitta* of the prior general Nicholas of France in 1271, “the only major Carmelite text which has survived from this period”.⁶

However, we now have access to another major Carmelite spiritual text from the 13th century or shortly after, a lengthy allegorical sermon on the Eucharist by the Cologne Carmelite, Conrad of Saint George.⁷ Hein Blommestijn—leaving aside Nicholas—calls him “the oldest spiritual writer of Carmel”,⁸ and he should perhaps be considered the first mystical writer of the Order.

Little is known of Conrad, and the sources are often late and contradictory.⁹ He was from a Cologne family from the parish of Saint George, from which he takes his name. The Carmelite house, which

³ For the various redactions of the text to 1369, cf. STARING, *MCH*, 33-43.

⁴ STARING, *MCH*, 44-48.

⁵ STARING, *MCH*, 71-90.

⁶ RICHARD COPSEY, “The *Ignea Sagitta* and Its Readership: A Re-Evaluation,” *Carmelus* 46 (1999): 164-73. For the text see ADRIANUS STARING, ed., “Nicolai prioris generalis Ordinis Carmelitarum Ignea sagitta,” *Carmelus* 9 (1962): 237-307. The best treatment is by ANDREW JOTISCHKY, *The Carmelites and Antiquity: Mendicants and Their Pasts in the Middle Ages* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002), 79-104.

⁷ Conrad’s sermon is one of the surprisingly few examples of medieval Carmelite preaching to have survived before the late 14th century: see PAUL CHANDLER, “The Lamentation of the Virgin: A *Planctus Mariae* Sermon by Michael Aiguani of Bologna, O.Carm.,” in *The Land of Carmel: Essays in Honor of Joachim Smet* (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1991), 209-10, n. 3. Recently RALF LÜTZELSCHWAB reports finding about 160, mostly unknown, surviving Carmelite sermons from the late 14th and 15th centuries, which dramatically opens up the field of Carmelite preaching to further study; however, he thought that none survive from the 13th or early 14th: “At Home in a New World? Carmelite Preaching and the Loss of Religious Identity,” in *Preaching and New Worlds: Sermons as Mirrors or Realms Near and Far*, ed. TIMOTHY JOHNSON, KATHERINE SHELBY, and JOHN YOUNG, Routledge Studies in Medieval Religion and Culture, vol. 13 (London: Routledge, 2020), 101-19, esp. 107, 110.

⁸ HEIN BLOMMESTIJN, “De Eucharistie in de vroege Karmelitaanse spiritualiteit,” in *De lengte en de breedte, de hoogte en de diepte: peilingen in de theologie van de sacramenten*, ed. A.H.C. VAN ELK and H.W.M. RIKHOF (Zoetemeer: Meinema, 1996), 39-73, at 73.

⁹ Biographical details are mainly drawn from ANDREAS H. SCHOLTEN, “Want dit cloestere is een paradijs Gods...: Spätmittelalterliche Predigten von Jan Pascha und Gielis de Leeuw zu Einkleidungs- und Professfeiern im Karmelittinnenkloster Vilvoorde bei Brüssel,” Ph.D. thesis. 3 vols (Westfälischen Wilhelms-Universität zu Münster, 2010), 1:23-28; <https://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:hbz:6-04389561112> (retrieved 18 June 2021).

had been founded in 1255/56, was in the same parish.¹⁰ Several sons joined the Carmelites, Conrad at some time before 1280. He appears to have been among the first German Carmelites to be sent to Paris for university studies, perhaps in 1281.¹¹ From sometime after 1295 to sometime before 1305 he was prior provincial of the Lower German Province (the dates are uncertain);¹² he served as prior of the convent in Cologne from 1305, perhaps until 1310.¹³ He seems to have been particularly remembered for his intervention, with his successor as provincial Gotfridus Wallraef, in the turbulence which had been provoked in the English province by the bitterly and long contested separation of the Irish and Scottish houses, reasserted by the general chapter of Narbonne in 1303. After much resistance, an unsuccessful intervention by the prior general, and appeals to the King and Pope Benedict XI, Cardinal Gentile da Montefiore sent Conrad and Wallraef to preside at a provincial chapter in London in 1305, where they enforced a drastic resolution by the deposition and banishment of the provincial, William Ludlyngton, and the dispersal to *studia* on the Continent of the leaders of the opposition.¹⁴

¹⁰ EDELTRAUD KLEUTING, "Köln, Waidmarkt", in EDELTRAUD KLEUTING, STEPHAN PANZER, and ANDREAS H. SCHOLTEN, *Monasticon Carmelitanum: Kloster des Karmeliterordens (O.Carm.) von den Anfängen bis in die Gegenwart*, Monastica Carmelitana, vol. 2 (Münster: Aschendorff, 2012), 386.

¹¹ FRANZ-BERNARD LICKTEIG, *The German Carmelites at the Medieval Universities*, Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana, vol. 13 (Roma: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1981), 118-119, 367, 425.

¹² SCHOLTEN, "Want dit cloestere is een paradijs Gods," 24. RICHARD COPSEY, *Biographical Register of Carmelites in England and Wales 1240-1540* (Faversham: St Albert's Press, 2020), 23, following LICKTEIG, *The German Carmelites at the Medieval Universities*, 367, thinks he was provincial only between 1298 and 1299/1300. See also BARTOLOMÉ MARÍA XIBERTA, *De scriptoribus scholasticis saeculi XIV ex ordine Carmelitarum*, Bibliothèque de la Revue d'Histoire Ecclésiastique, fasc. 6 (Louvain: Bureaux de la Revue, 1931), 113-14, n. 2, who gives 1298-1303; IRENAEUS ROSIER, *Biografisch en bibliografisch overzicht van de vroomheid in de Nederlandse Carmel van 1235 tot het midden der achttiende eeuw*, Studien en tekstuutgaven van Ons geestelijk erf, vol. 10 (Tiel: Lanoo, 1950), 23, gives 1295-1303; and cf. H.H. KOCH, *Die Karmelitenklöster der Niederdeutschen Provinz 13. bis 16. Jahrhundert*, (Freiburg im Breisgau: Herdersche Verlagshandlung, 1896), 28, where the sequence of priors provincial lists Conrad from 1296 and Wallraef from 1303.

¹³ KLEUTING, PANZER, AND SCHOLTEN, *Monasticon Carmelitanum*, 411.

¹⁴ The incident is known from an account preserved by John Bale: XIBERTA, *De Script.*, 113; JOACHIM SMET, *The Carmelites: A History of the Brothers of Our Lady of Mount Carmel*, 4 vols in 5 (Darren, IL: Carmelite Spiritual Center, 1976-88), 1:44-45; *Monumenta Historica Carmelitana*, ed. BENEDICT ZIMMERMAN (Lérins: Ex typis abbatiae, 1905-7), 225-227; KEITH J. EGAN, "The Establishment and Early Development of the Carmelite Order in England," Ph.D. thesis (University of Cambridge, 1965), 306-11; I

Conrad would have been a contemporary of the first generation of Carmelite masters and theological writers in the first quarter of the 14th century, perhaps slightly older than most: Gerard of Bologna, the Order's first known master of theology, Simon of Corbie, the second, Peter Swannington, Robert Walsingham, Gui Terreni, and Sibert de Beek, the last also from the convent of Cologne. Their theological production starts after 1300. However, Conrad is the only one to have left a substantial spiritual work.¹⁵

It is not known with certainty when Conrad died. Although 1305 was commonly given as the year of his death, it was perhaps as late as 1316 or '17.¹⁶

The bibliographers of the Order knew Conrad as an author. Cosmas de Villiers' *Bibliotheca Carmelitana*, the 1752 bio-bibliographical encyclopedia of Carmelite authors which has been a principal reference until the present, lists three works by him, of which he knew no surviving manuscripts or editions. De Villiers' entry is:

Conrad of Saint George, of the German nation, Carmelite, doctor and professor of Sacred Theology. He was the *socius* of Gobelinus [Gotfridus Wallraef], who were sent to England by Boniface VIII [probably Benedict XI] about the year 1302 [1305] to put an end to a certain schism among the Carmelites, some supporting the division of the province and others opposing it. Our Conrad was provincial of Lower Germany, and wrote:

1. *De Eucharistia Sacramento*. Lib. I.
2. *Quaestiones varias*. Lib. I.
3. *Lecturas Theologicas*. Lib. I.

By way of a note De Villiers gives as his sources Josias Simmler's edition of Conrad Gessner's monumental *Bibliotheca Universalis*,

am grateful to Dr Egan for making these pages of his thesis available. See also RICHARD COPSEY, "The Scottish Carmelite Province and Its Provincials", in PAUL CHANDLER and KEITH J. EGAN, eds., *The Land of Carmel: Essays in Honor of Joachim Smet* (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1991), 189–208; cf. COPSEY, *Biographical Register*, 23–24, 52–53.

¹⁵ XIBERTA, *De Script.*, *passim*; CHRISTOPHER SCHABEL, "Carmelite *Quodlibeta*," in *Theological Quodlibeta in the Middle Ages. Vol. 2: The Fourteenth Century*, ed. CHRISTOPHER SCHABEL, Brill's Companions to the Christian Tradition, vol. 7 (Leiden: Brill, 2007), 493–541. A young Sibert is possibly the author of *Universis christifidelibus* around 1289: STARING, *MCH*, 79–80; John Baconthorpe, another early master, begins his spiritual writing about the Order only after 1317: STARING, *MCH*, 176–77.

¹⁶ SCHOLTEN, "Want dit cloestere is een paradijs Gods," 23, n. 47.

which had first appeared in 1545, Paulus Segeri, Louis Jacob, and the *Speculum Carmelitanum* of Daniel of the Virgin Mary.¹⁷

Conrad's name was absent from the first edition of Simmler's version of Gessner in 1555,¹⁸ but was included in the edition of 1574, with the asterisk indicating that it is a new entry.¹⁹ It already contains what remain the basic known facts of Conrad's biography, except that what Simmler lists as two works become three in De Villiers:

* Conrad of Saint George, German, Carmelite, with the German Gobelini a commissioner to the English to settle a certain schism. He wrote *De Eucharistia Sacramento* lib. 1, and *Quaestiones & lecturas* lib. 1. He died in 1305.²⁰

Conrad's works were all thought to be lost. However, in 1993 the present author noticed a reference to Conrad's work on the Eucharist in Middle Dutch translation in a miscellany manuscript in Vienna, which had been first described in detail by Albert Ampe as part of his

¹⁷ COSMÉ DE SAINT ETIENNE DE VILLIERS, *Bibliotheca Carmelitana, notis criticis et dissertationibus illustrata*, ed. GABRIEL WESSELS (Orléans, 1752; repr. Rome: in aedibus Collegii S. Alberti, 1927), I, col. 352: "Conradus de S. Georgio, natione Germanus, Carmelita, sacrae Theologiae Doctor ac Professor. Is socius fuit Gobelini Teutonici, à Bonfacio VIII. in Angliam missi circa annum 1302 pro secundo quodam schismate inter Carmelitas orto, Provinciae subdivisionem alios postulantes, alios e contra negantes. Conradus noster Provincialis fuit Germaniae inferioris, & scripsit:

1. *De Eucharistia Sacramento*. Lib. I.
2. *Quaestiones varias*. Lib. I
3. *Lecturas Theologicas*. Lib. I.

Ita Josias Simmler, in *Epitome Gesneriana*. Et de illo mentionem facit Paulus Segeri, *Lib. de Viris illustribus Ordinis Carmelitani*: quem secuti sunt Ludovicus Jacob, in *Bibliotheca Carmelitana* Ms. pag. 64. Daniel à Virgine Maria, tom. 2. *Speculi Carmelitani*, pag. 1096, num. 3875."

¹⁸ JOSIAS SIMMLER, *Epitome Bibliothecae Conradi Gesneri conscripta primum à Conrado Lycosthene Rubeaquensi: nunc denuo recognita & plus quàm bis mille authorum accessione (qui omnes asterisco signati sunt) locupletata per Iosiam Simlervm Tigvrvnm* (Zürich: Froshauer, 1555).

¹⁹ JOSIAS SIMMLER and CONRAD GESSNER, *Bibliotheca instituta et collecta primum a Conrado Gesnero, deinde [a Conrado Lycosthene] in epitomen redacta & novorum librorum accessione locupletata, jam vero postremo recognita, & in duplum post priores editiones aucta, per Josiam Simlervm...* (Zürich: apud Christophorum Froshoverum, 1574), 136.

²⁰ "*Conradus de S. Georgio, Germanus, Carmelita, cum Gobelino Alemanno, pro sedando quodam schismate commisarius ad Anglos, scripsit *De Eucharistia Sacramento*, lib.1. *Quaestiones & lecturas* lib.1. Claruit anno D. 1305."; SIMMLER and GESSNER, *Bibliotheca instituta et collecta*, 136.

work on Ruusbroec.²¹ This manuscript, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, cod. 15419, originally from the Convent of St Elisabeth auf dem Berg Sion in Brussels, seems to have been compiled around 1490. The first section (ff. 1r-58r) is a collection of texts in Middle Dutch on the Trinity and the Sacraments from Albert the Great, Ruusbroec, Jacques de Vitry, and the *Imitation of Christ*, and includes, still with the Latin incipit *Confiteantur Domino* (Psalm 106:31), “a glorious sermon on the Blessed Sacrament by Brother Conrad of Saint George, born in Cologne, of the Order of Our Blessed Lady”.²²

Hein Blommestijn, O.Carm., worked further on the Middle Dutch versions of Conrad’s work, including two further manuscripts which had been identified by Ampe:²³ Tilburg University, Universiteitsbibliotheek, Ms. UB I, 20 (KHS 20, *olim* PGNB 647), ff. 20v-52v: *Een seer devoet sermoen vanden werden heijligen sacrament*;²⁴ and The Hague, Koninklijke Bibliotheek, Ms. 73 H 30 (K 40), ff. 106v-122v: *Dat van den heiligen sacrament*.²⁵ However, none of these Middle Dutch manuscripts represents the whole text. Conrad divided his sermon into six parts: Tilburg has parts two and three; The Hague part three; and the Vienna manuscript is a summary text of the whole. Blommestijn notes that part three shows many textual variations between the versions in the Tilburg and The Hague manuscripts, and suspects that

²¹ ALBERT AMPE, “Kritisch onderzoek van enkele aan Ruusbroec toegeschreven teksten,” in *Dr. L. Reyens-Album. Opstellen aangeboden aan Prof. Dr. L. Reyens s.j. ter gelegenheid van zijn tachtigste verjaardag op 26 februari 1964* (Antwerpen: Ruusbroec-Genootschap, 1964), 23–30, 31–34. The 19th-century catalog included Conrad’s work under the generic phrase “et aliorum plurium”; *Tabulae codicum manu scriptorum praeter graecos et orientales in Bibliotheca Palatina Vindobonensi asservatorum*, 8 vols, ed. Academia Caesarea Vindobonensis (Vienna: Gerold, 1864–99), 8:160–61. A fuller description in 1961 attracted little attention: HERMANN MENHART, *Verzeichnis der altdeutschen literarischen Handschriften der österreichischen Nationalbibliothek*, 13 vols, Deutsche Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin: Veröffentlichungen des Instituts für deutsche Sprache und Literatur (Berlin: Akademie Verlag, 1961), 3:1423–24. Ampe noted in 1964 that this important miscellany manuscript was unknown and unexploited; AMPE, “Kritisch Onderzoek,” 23.

²² “Hier beghint een glorioes sermo vanden heyleghen sacramente, dat maecte broeder coenraet van sent iorys geboren van cuelen der ordenen onser liever vrouwen”; MENHART, *Verzeichnis*, 3:1423–24.

²³ BLOMMESTIJN, “De Eucharistie”, esp. 41–45.

²⁴ For the catalog description see JEROEN M.M. VAN DE VEN, *Over Brabant geschreven: handschriften en archivalische bronnen in de Tilburgse Universiteitsbibliotheek (deel 1)*, *Miscellanea Neerlandica*, vol. 8 (Leuven: Peeters, 1994), 118–26.

²⁵ A catalog description is at <https://opc-kb.oclc.org/DB=1/XMLPRS=Y/PPN?PPN=310829666> (accessed 7 July 2021).

they may be two different translations “of a thus far unknown Latin original”.²⁶ It is this Latin original which is now presented below.

The manuscript in the Royal Library in The Hague dates from around 1460, and belonged to the Regular Canonesses of the Saint Agnes convent in Maaseik. It contains Ruusbroec’s *Spiegel der ewiger salicheit* (*Speculum salutis aeternae*) and some other treatises and sermons on the Eucharist. The manuscript in Tilburg, dated to the first quarter of the 16th century, is a collection of meditations and prayers probably from the circle of the author of the highly influential mystical text *Evangelische Peerle* (now thought to be Reinalda van Eymeren of the Saint Agnes convent in Arnhem).²⁷ Among the authors are Augustine, Anselm, John of Fécamp, and Thomas a Kempis. Together with the Vienna manuscript, the circulation of Conrad’s work in vernacular versions under his name in collections of well-known mystical writers shows that his sermon was esteemed for centuries in devout circles of the Low Countries, in general associated with Rhineland mysticism and the affective piety of the *Devotio moderna*.

The Latin text

The “lost” Latin original was hiding in plain sight, either circulated anonymously or misattributed to Saint Bonaventure.²⁸ It was the distinguished Bonaventure scholar Jacques Guy Bougerol, OFM, who enabled its reattribution to Conrad of Saint George by noticing his identification as author in manuscript 987 of the Bibliothèque Mazarine in Paris.²⁹ Bougerol, it seems, was not aware of the Middle

²⁶ “Maar het is ook goed mogelijk dat beide afhankelijk zijn van een dusver onbekend Latijns origineel, waarvan we twee Middelnederlandse vertalingen/bewerkingen bezitten”; BLOMMESTIJN, “De Eucharistie,” 44.

²⁷ On the mystical movement associated with the convent of Saint Agnes, see INEKE CORNET, *The Arnhem Mystical Sermons: Preaching Liturgical Mysticism in the Context of Catholic Reform*, Brill’s Series in Church History, vol. 77 (Leiden: Brill, 2018).

²⁸ It is the third of five “Sermones de rebus theologis” in vol. 5 of the Quaracchi edition of Bonaventure’s complete works; “Sermo III,” in *Doctoris seraphici S. Bonaventurae... opera omnia. Vol. V: Opuscula varia theologica* (Quaracchi: ex typographia Collegii S. Bonaventurae, 1891), 553–56.

²⁹ JACQUES GUY BOUGEROL, “Le manuscrit Paris Mazarine 987 et le sermon ‘Confiteantur’ faussement attribué à Saint Bonaventure,” *Archivum Franciscanum Historicum* 86 (1993): 3–17; cf. idem, SAINT BONAVENTURE, *Sermons de Diversis*, ed. JACQUES GUY BOUGEROL (Paris: Editions Franciscaines, 1993), 50. The catalogue record for ms. 987 is at <http://www.calames.abes.fr/pub/mazarine.aspx#details?id=MAZA14199> (accessed 1 July 2021).

Dutch translations, which provide independent evidence of Conrad's authorship.

Bougerol lists thirty-six manuscripts of the sermon "Confiteantur", saying that the list is not exhaustive. Of these, eight are attributed to Bonaventure, and only the Mazarine manuscript to Conrad. The remainder appear to be anonymous. Titles vary, with "De corpore Christi" being common (the traditional and most common title, which I suggest should continue to be used), with "De sacramento altaris" in the incipit of the Mazarine manuscript, and "De corpore Christi" in the explicit.

The manuscripts listed by Bougerol, with the exception of Mazarine 987 (from Brabant), are from Austria and Bavaria, with one each also from Poland and Moravia in today's Czech Republic; twelve are from the Bayerische Staatsbibliothek in Munich, formerly from religious houses in Bavaria.³⁰ The preponderance of German-language areas in this distribution puzzled Bonaventure's Franciscan editors, who theorised that the sermon must have been given during Bonaventure's travels in Germany in 1259 or in the winter of 1270/71, while others speculatively linked it to Orvieto in 1264 in the context of the introduction of the feast of Corpus Christi by Urban IV.³¹

Bougerol's list, dependent for sixteen manuscripts on the 1891 work of the Quaracchi editors, has at least one error,³² and even a cursory search finds nine additional manuscripts, which would have to be taken into account for an eventual critical edition.³³ Further

³⁰ BOUGEROL, "Le manuscrit Paris Mazarine 987," 4.

³¹ *Doctoris Seraphici s. Bonaventurae. Opera Theologica Selecta: Editio Minor*, 5 vols (Quaracchi: Ex typographia Collegio S. Bonaventura, 1934), 18*; BALDUINUS DISTELBRINK, *Bonaventurae scripta: authentica, dubia vel spuria critice recensita*, Subsidia Scientifica Franciscalia, vol. 5 (Roma: Istituto Storico Cappuccini, 1975), 81–82; FRANCISCO CHAVERO BLANCO, "El catálogo de las obras de san Buenaventura: estado actual de la cuestión," *Carthaginensia: Revista de estudios e investigación* 14 (1998): 65.

³² Munich, Staatsbibliothek, Clm 3737, Bougerol's no. 16 and Quaracchi's no. 11, is not a 15th-century ms. containing Conrad's work but a 12th-century ms. of the Commentary of the Venerable Bede on the Gospel of Mark; cf. KARL FELIX HALM, et al., *Catalogus codicum latinorum Bibliothecae Regiae Monacensis. 1,2: Codices num. 2501–5250 complectens*, ed. altera emendatior (Munich: Bibliotheca Regia, 1894), 129. There is a newer description at <http://www.manuscripta-mediaevalia.de/#/5> (retrieved 24 June 2021).

³³ Augsburg, Staats- und Stadtbibliothek, fol. cod. 273, ff. 163r-166v; Brno, Státní Oblastní Arch., Cerr II, c.198; Graz, Universitätsbibliothek, ms. 1128, ff. 35v-46r; Leipzig, Universitätsbibliothek, ms. 426, ff. 273–276; Lüneberg, Ratsbucherei, ms. theol. quart. 57, ff. 329v-337v; Munich, Staatsbibliothek, Clm 14294, ff. 27v-126r; Munich, Universitätsbibliothek, ms. fol. 1437, ff. 120v-126r; Olomouc, V deká knihovna, M I 302; Ottobeuren, Kloster Ottobeuren, ms. O.42, ff. 262r-276r.

work is likely to show that Conrad's sermon was quite popular and widely diffused, both under the prestigious name of Bonaventure and more often as an anonymous work. It was already highly regarded in the 14th century (in the Mazarine manuscript it is called "a glorious sermon").³⁴

How did it come to be included among the works of Saint Bonaventure? It seems that the work was already being occasionally attributed to Bonaventure by the last quarter of the 14th century (Klosterneuburg, Stiftsbibliothek, ms. 251 is perhaps from the 1370s).³⁵ The sermon was not known to the editors of the Vatican edition of 1588–96 or those immediately succeeding,³⁶ and from the 17th century onwards there has been long-lasting debate about the authenticity of many works attributed to Bonaventure.³⁷ In the modern history of Bonaventure's works Conrad's sermon was first published in Benedetto Bonelli's 1774 edition of the *Opera Omnia*. He used a transcription made in 1765 by the Benedictine Urbanus Schaukegl from a 15th-century manuscript in the Abbey of Göttweig in Austria.³⁸ In effect, then, the first modern attribution of Conrad's sermon to Bonaventure was based on a single manuscript.

In 1767, in preparation for his edition, Bonelli had addressed issues of authenticity in his *Prodromus ad opera omnia S. Bonaventurae*. He lists the sermon *De corpore Christi* among the unedited works of the saint, arguing for its authenticity on purely internal grounds, "because it everywhere breathes devotion, charity, love of the

³⁴ *Explicit gloriosus sermo de corpore Christi*, f. 57r.

³⁵ FRANZ LACKNER, *Katalog der Handschriften des Augustiner Chorherrenstiftes Klosterneuburg, Teil 3: Cod. 201-300*, (Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, phil.-hist. Klasse, Denkschriften 434 = Veröffentlichungen zum Schrift- und Buchwesen des Mittelalters II,2,3). Wien 2012; https://manuscripta.at/hs_detail.php?ID=410 (retrieved 16 June 2021).

³⁶ *Sancti Bonaventurae S.R.E. Cardinalis... Opera...* 7 vols, (Rome: ex typographia Vaticana, 1588–96). See also the chart of editions in PIETRO MARANESI, "The *Opera Omnia* of Saint Bonaventure: History and Present Situation," in *A Companion to Bonaventure*, ed. JAY HAMMOND, WAYNE HELLMANN, and JARED GOFF, Brill's Companions to the Christian Tradition, vol. 48 (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 67–68.

³⁷ JACQUES GUY BOUGEROL, *Introduction à Saint Bonaventure*, A la Recherche de la Verité (Paris: Librairie Philosophique J. Vrin, 1988); MARANESI, "The *Opera Omnia* of Saint Bonaventure," 61–68.

³⁸ BENEDETTO BONELLI, *Sancti Bonaventurae ex Ordine Minorum... Operum Omnium... Supplementum in tria volumina distributum* (Trent: ex typographia episcopali Joannis Baptistae Monauni, 1774), 3:952–84; "Prolegomena in sermones selectos de rebus theologicis," in *Opuscula varia theologica*, vol. 5, *Doctoris Seraphici S. Bonaventurae S.R.E. Episc. Card. Opera Omnia* (Quaracchi: ex typographia Collegii S. Bonaventurae, 1891), xlvi.

Cross, and contempt of the world; everywhere it bubbles with the mystical sense of the sacred Scriptures; it has quotations from Ambrose, Augustine, Gregory, Isidore, Bernard, and the Gloss; and it has many affinities with things that are taught by Bonaventure elsewhere..."³⁹ Once the sermon had thus entered into the Bonaventuran corpus, his editors were reluctant to let it go, mainly arguing for his authorship from its theological quality and profundity, which they were confident must indicate Bonaventure's authorship.

The 19th-century Quaracchi editors acknowledged that many of the miscellaneous theological sermons attributed to Bonaventure in the Vatican edition were spurious, and they retained only five. While admitting that authenticity remained an "arduous issue", they argued for Bonaventuran authorship of this and another sermon on the grounds that "they so abound in richness of doctrine and so reveal the genius of the author that no hesitation could arise about giving them a place here", and this remained more or less the standard opinion.⁴⁰ The apparatus of the 1891 edition is full of references to parallel passages in Bonaventure's works as detailed argument for his putative authorship. *De corpore Christi* was included in the *editio minor* with a note justifying its inclusion because of "both its abundant and profound teaching... and also its limpid style and charming eloquence".⁴¹ Franz Xaver Kattum called the sermon "the masterpiece of Eucharistic mysticism".⁴² Ephrem Longpré called it "the admirable

³⁹ *Prodromus ad opera omnia S. Bonaventurae... agens de ejus vita, doctrina et scriptis editis ac ineditis, recensque inter vetustos codices manuscriptos inventis in libros octo tributus* (Bassano: sumptibus Remondini Veneti, 1767), col. 748: "Fuisse autem Doctorem Devotum ac Seraphicum Bonaventuram, vel inde conjici posse, quia talis Sermo ubique spirat devotionem, caritatem, crucis amorem, ac saeculi contemptum: scatet ubique mystico divinarum Scripturarum sensu: allegationes insertas habet Ambrosii, Augustini, Gregorii, Isidoris, Bernardi, et Glossae; pluraque continet affinia illis quae alibi a D. Bonaventurae docentur..."

⁴⁰ "Prolegomena in sermones selectos"; *Doctoris seraphici S. Bonaventurae... opera omnia. Vol. V: Opuscula varia theologica* (Quaracchi: ex typographia Collegii S. Bonaventurae, 1891), xlv: "Sermo igitur secundus de regno Dei et tertius de Ss. Corpore Christi adeo doctrinae copia abundans et ingenium auctoris manifestans, ut de loco ipsis hic concedendo nulla potuerit oriri haesitatio."

⁴¹ SAINT BONAVENTURE, *Opera Theologica Selecta*, 5:17-18: "Mereretur hunc titulum tum propter copiosam et profundam doctrinam his propositam tum propter stilum limpidum et facundiam amoenam". The later edition of 1964 admitted that "it cannot be denied" that there were also reasons to doubt its authenticity; quoted in BOUGEROL, "Le manuscrit Paris Mazarine 987," 7.

⁴² *Die Eucharistielehre des heil. Bonaventura* (München-Freising: Datterer, 1920), 2; quoted in *Dictionnaire d'histoire et de géographie ecclésiastiques*, s.v. "Bonaventure, Saint" (Paris: Letouzey et Ané, 1937), vol. 9, cols 755-769.

conference”, and drew on it extensively for his treatment of Bonaventure’s spirituality and Mariology in the entry on the saint in the *Dictionnaire de Spiritualité*.⁴³ Oscar Righi calls this “great sermon” the proof that Bonaventure was closely involved in the movement of eucharistic devotion which marked the last months of the pontificate of Urban IV in 1264.⁴⁴ Although Ignatius Brady’s suspicions had been aroused by the distribution of the manuscripts and the lack of attribution to Bonaventure,⁴⁵ as recently as 1975 Balduinus Distelbrink declared for its authenticity in his important evaluation of the works in the Bonaventuran corpus, calling it “this sublime and rich sermon, most certainly authentic... replete with profound theological teaching and shining splendidly with seraphic ardor”.⁴⁶ However, Bougerol’s study and now the link with vernacular translations mean that authorship must be reassigned from Bonaventure to Conrad.⁴⁷

What was the context of Conrad’s sermon? It was evidently addressed to religious (§25–27: “one must flee the consolation of this world and enter religious life”), but of what kind is not clear. Ann Astell suggested it should be understood in the context of Franciscan efforts to portray Saint Francis as a new Elijah, but this was when it was still attributed to Bonaventure.⁴⁸ Charles Caspers has suggested placing in it in the context of the interest in biblical prefigurations of the Eucharist sparked by the new forms of eucharistic piety in the late 13th century, anticipated by Caesarius of Heisterbach and Thomas Aquinas, and it would be interesting to consider how Conrad fits

⁴³ *Dictionnaire de Spiritualité*, s.v. “Bonaventure, Saint”, (Paris: Beauchesne, 1932), vol. 1, col. 1771.

⁴⁴ *Il pensiero e l’opera di San Bonaventura da Bagnoregio* (Firenze: Le Monnier, 1932), 261–274.

⁴⁵ IGNATIUS BRADY, “The Opera Omnia of St. Bonaventure Revisited,” *Proceedings of the American Catholic Philosophical Association* 48 (1974): 299.

⁴⁶ BALDUINUS DISTELBRINK, *Bonaventurae scripta: authentica, dubia vel spuria critica recensita*, Subsidia Scientifica Franciscalia, vol. 5 (Roma: Istituto Storico Cappuccini, 1975), 81–82: “Iste sermo sublimis et copiosus, satis certe authenticus... profunda doctrina theologica refertus ac ardore seraphico luculenter enitens”.

⁴⁷ Cf. MARANESI, “The Opera Omnia of Saint Bonaventure,” 78.

⁴⁸ ANN W. ASTELL, *Eating Beauty: The Eucharist and the Spiritual Arts of the Middle Ages* (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2006), 131–135. On the comparison of Elijah and St Francis see also JOHN V. FLEMING, *From Bonaventure to Bellini: An Essay in Franciscan Exegesis* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1982), 64–74; and MARIANNE SCHLOSSER, “‘Princeps noster Elias’: der Prophet Elija als Vorbild monastischen Lebens,” *Edith-Stein-Jahrbuch* 8 (2002): 48–64.

within these developments.⁴⁹ Hein Blommestijn has suggested a connection with the mystical piety of women in the period, certainly worth exploring.⁵⁰

Conrad writes in the tradition of affective mystical devotion which has long been associated with the Cistercians, Franciscans, and late medieval female piety, and his debt to Bernard of Clairvaux is evident. However, Lauren Mancía has now traced affective piety—as “a process of human intentionality and self-presence”—to earlier monastic sources, especially John of Fécamp (†1079), and Robert Davis has argued for a rethinking of the whole traditional narrative of affective piety.⁵¹ Conrad shares the Christocentric affectivity of this long tradition: his Jesus is all sweetness, the encounter with him a source of delight. Conrad is particularly interested in the reshaping of the self: the “stretching of the soul” (§14) through charity, devotion, the habit of gratitude, integrity of intention, commitment to personal growth, attention to the Passion of Christ, the cultivation and discipline of desire, the habit of prayer, devotion to the Virgin, an eye on eternal life. Although he is relatively unsystematic, he proposes such “technologies of the self” in service of spiritual rebirth through grace.⁵²

Theologically, Conrad reflects the developing eucharistic theology of his period, with its more precise definition of substance and accidents in the sacrament, its emphasis on bringing the believer into an increasingly intense spiritual relationship with Christ, and the

⁴⁹ CHARLES CASPERS, “Wandering Between Transubstantiation and Transfiguration: Images of the Prophet Elijah in Western Christianity, 1200–1500 CE,” in *Saints and Role Models in Judaism and Christianity*, ed. M. BASIL PENNINGTON, JOSHUA SCHWARTZ, and MARCEL POORTHUIS, Jewish and Christian Perspectives Series, vol. 7 (Leiden: Brill, 2004), 335–54.

⁵⁰ BLOMMESTIJN, “De Eucharistie,” 73. See also, for example, BARBARA R. WALTERS, ed., *The Feast of Corpus Christi* (University Park, Pa.: Pennsylvania State University Press, 2006).

⁵¹ LAUREN MANCÍA, *Emotional Monasticism: Affective Piety in the Eleventh-Century Monastery of John of Fécamp*, Artes Liberales (Manchester: UK Manchester University Press, 2019), esp. 195, where she is quoting BERNARD MCGINN, “Mystical Consciousness: A Modest Proposal,” *Spiritus* 8 (2008): 46; ROBERT GLENN DAVIS, *The Weight of Love: Affect, Ecstasy, and Union in the Theology of Bonaventure* (New York: Fordham University Press, 2017), 1–28.

⁵² LUTHER H. MARTIN, et al., *Technologies of the Self: A Seminar with Michel Foucault* (Amherst: University of Massachusetts Press, 1988); and for the antiquity of this tradition in Christian monasticism see especially INBAR GRAIVER, *Asceticism of the Mind: Forms of Attention and Self-Transformation in Late Antique Monasticism*, Studies and Texts, vol. 213 (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 2018).

conviction of its effect in the growth of an active life of faith and charity.⁵³

The content of the sermon

The contemplative reading of scripture was at the heart of Carmelite life: the Rule required “meditating on the Law of the Lord day and night” (par. 10).⁵⁴ In their approach to pondering scripture medieval religious had at their disposal the elaborate system of interpretation known as the “four senses of sacred scripture”, which derives from the Alexandrian school, Origen, John Cassian, and Augustine.⁵⁵ A famous mnemonic verse, apparently from Conrad’s near contemporary Augustine of Dacia, OP, summed it up: *Littera gesta docet, quid credas allegoria, / Moralis quid agas, quid speres anagogia* (“The literal reading teaches what happened, the allegorical what you ought to believe, the moral what you should do, and the anagogical what you should hope for”), though the last three were often collapsed into a less differentiated “spiritual” or “mystical” sense.⁵⁶

Conrad’s sermon is fundamentally concerned with Christian conversion and mystical transformation and so especially with the moral sense, but his method is firmly allegorical, even flamboyantly

⁵³ For a summary see especially GARY MACY, “Theology of the Eucharist in the High Middle Ages,” in *A Companion to the Eucharist in the Middle Ages*, ed. IAN CHRISTOPHER LEVY, GARY MACY, and KRISTEN VAN AUDSALL, Brill’s Companions to the Christian Tradition, vol. 26 (Leiden: Brill, 2012), 365–97.

⁵⁴ On *lectio divina* in the Rule see, for example, CICONETTI, *La Regola*, 665–71 and the index. The text of the Rule from the bull *Que honorem Conditoris* of Innocent IV (1 October 1247) is in EVALDO XAVIER GOMES, et al., ed., *The Carmelite Rule 1207–2007: Proceedings of the Lisieux Conference, 4–7 July 2005*, Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana, vol. 28 (Rome: Edizioni Carmelitane, 2008), 625–28 and elsewhere. The most accessible text of the Rule in English is at <https://ocarm.org/en/item/5438-the-carmelite-rule-text> (retrieved 29 June 2021).

⁵⁵ The standard study is HENRI DE LUBAC, *Exegèse médiévale: les quatre sens de l’écriture*, 4 vols (Paris: Aubier, 1959–64); three volumes have been translated into English: *Medieval Exegesis: The Four Senses of Scripture*, 3 vols, Ressourcement (Grand Rapids, Mich.: William B. Eerdmans, 1998–2009).

⁵⁶ KURT VILLADS JENSEN, “Augustinus de Dacia”, in STEPHAN BORGEHAMMAR et al., ed., *Medieval Nordic Literature in Latin: A Website of Authors and Anonymous Works c. 1100–1530*, https://wiki.uib.no/medieval/index.php/Augustinus_de_Dacia (accessed 7 July 2021). The last line is usually given in a variant form as *quo tendas anagogia* “the anagogical where you are heading”.

so.⁵⁷ The smallest details of the biblical text become the foundation for complex structures of meaning, in ways that the modern reader may find perplexing. Even in Conrad's own time there was unease about the extravagance of some allegorical readings, for example from the famous Franciscan biblicist Nicholas of Lyra.⁵⁸ In recent decades, however, especially under the influence of postmodern literary criticism, there has been a renewed appreciation of allegorical modes of interpretation. Mark Burrows, writing on Saint Bernard of Clairvaux's allegorical method, says that "it seeks to unfold not what the text *meant* but what it *means* for present readers". Allegory becomes "a kind of fiction", "a carefully calculated subversion of the text's plain meaning", not so much "as a separate *sense* but as a particular way of *reading*" which seeks to create a new meaning from the text which serves the construction of the converted monastic self, its purpose "not so much to explain words as to move hearts".⁵⁹

Delight arises from the apparently infinite variety and complexity of exploratory paths, and the reader's enjoyment depends upon the difficulty encountered and the exertion this calls forth. The text as labyrinth for the dream-like experience of monastic reading provides a locus for wandering, a maze for searching, which as a journey into the mysterious darkness of one's own interior is itself a discovery... Understood in this manner, allegory is the formal expression of an unending search, a seemingly boundless quest undertaken within the bounded textual world of scripture. As an interior journey, the search functioned as an existential mode of reading based upon patterns of meaning crucial for the experience of attaining monastic conversion... These patterns were to be discovered primarily in the *interpreter*, and only secondarily as rules applied to the text.⁶⁰

⁵⁷ On the renewed appreciation of pre-modern exegesis, see for example: DAVIS C. STEINMETZ, "The Superiority of Pre-Critical Exegesis," *Theology Today* 37.1 (1980): 27–38; MARIE ANN MAYESKI, "Quaestio Disputata: Catholic Theology and the History of Exegesis," *Theological Studies* 62 (2001): 140–53; DANIEL BOYARIN, "Origen as Theorist of Allegory: Alexandrian Contexts," in *Cambridge Companion to Allegory*, ed. RITA COPELAND and PETER T. STRUCK, Cambridge Companions to Literature (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 39–54; WILLIAM M. WRIGHT, "Patristic Exegetical Theory and Practice in De Lubac and Congar," *New Blackfriars* 96.1061 (2015): 61–73.

⁵⁸ DENYS TURNER, "Allegory in Christian Late Antiquity," in *Cambridge Companion to Allegory*, 71–82.

⁵⁹ MARK S. BURROWS, "Hunters, Hounds, and Allegorical Readers: The Body of the Text and the Text of the Body in Bernard of Clairvaux's *Sermons on the Song of Songs*," *Studies in Spirituality* 14 (2004): 114–15, 127–28, 137.

⁶⁰ BURROWS, "Hunters, Hounds, and Allegorical Readers," 123–24.

Conrad's text is generally called a sermon (*sermo*), though it has few signs of orality, and as many sermons did, overlaps with the genre of a treatise (*tractatus*).⁶¹ It does not strictly follow the prescriptions of the *Artes praedicandi*,⁶² and it lacks the exempla which were such a prominent and colourful part of popular preaching.⁶³ Conrad begins with the biblical *thema*, *Confiteantur Domino...* from Psalm 106:8–10 (which will be repeated to mark the end of each section): "Let the mercies of the Lord give glory to him, and his wonderful works to the children of men. For he has satisfied the empty soul, and filled the hungry soul with good things, those who sat in darkness and in the shadow of death, bound in want and in iron". He omits the usual protheme, a profession of humility or a request for a prayer for the preacher, and passes rather to the *divisio thematis*,⁶⁴ an introduction which sets the context for the sermon, whose theme is the need for openness to the action of grace on the "multiple shortcomings of our unhappy condition", of which there are six according to the Psalm: humankind is empty, without the Spirit of God; hungry, lacking spiritual food; in darkness, without divine knowledge; in the shadow of death, destined for damnation; in poverty, unable to act with virtue; iron-bound, obstinate in heart. These conditions will be remedied by six works of grace of the self-giving God: emptiness by the divine indwelling; hunger by spiritual food; darkness by illumination of hearts; the shadow of death by the offering of reconciliation; poverty by the work of virtue; obstinacy by the softening of hearts. These will be the six sections of Conrad's sermon, each developed through the allegorical interpretation of a biblical text.

Conrad's overarching metaphorical structure is grounded in the concrete realities of food and digestion, nourishment and assimilation. He will quote (§12) the famous line from Augustine's *Confessions* where Christ says, "You will not change me into yourself like bodily

⁶¹ BEVERLY MAYNE KIENZLE, ed., *The Sermon*, Typologie des sources du Moyen Age occidental, fasc. 81–83 (Turnhout: Brepols, 2000), 161, 168–71.

⁶² MARIANNE G. BRISCOE and BARBARA H. JAYE, 'Artes praedicandi' et 'Artes orandi', Typologie des Sources du Moyen Age Occidental, vol. 61 (Turnhout: Brepols, 1992); SIEGFRIED WENZEL, *Medieval Artes Praedicandi: A Synthesis of Scholastic Sermon Structure* (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2015), esp. 47–86.

⁶³ Cf. JEAN-CLAUDE SCHMITT, *Prêcher d'exemples: récits de prédicateurs du Moyen Age* (Paris: Stock, 1985); CARLO DELCORNO, *Exemplum e letteratura: tra Medioevo e Rinascimento* (Bologna: Mulino, 1989); Wenzel, *Medieval Artes Praedicandi*, 111–12.

⁶⁴ WENZEL, *Medieval Artes Praedicandi*, 65–75.

food, you will be changed into me”.⁶⁵ As Miri Rubin has noted about the eucharistic piety of the 13th century, “The eucharist developed into something good to eat, it could be experienced directly and assimilated into one’s body. The gift of food was the most satisfying of offerings, directly experienced and lovingly given...”, a sacrament of transformation and incorporation.⁶⁶

Conrad proceeds with the introduction of the six “figures” (or symbols, or images) (*figurae*) by which the Body of Christ is prefigured in the Hebrew scriptures. These six figures—fat, bread, honey, the paschal lamb, heavenly treasure, manna—each interpreted allegorically, will structure the sermon, which will be further developed by series of cascading subdivisions, almost always in groups of four.⁶⁷

The central part of the sermon takes up each of the six figures in turn. The first figure is “fat” (*pinguedo*), taken from a reference in Genesis 49:20, “Asher’s food shall be fat, and he shall provide delicacies to kings”. From this apparently unlikely text Conrad builds a case that the Body of Christ is given to preserve divine fervour in the heart, which is preserved in three ways: through delight within oneself, through love of neighbour, and through devotion to God. The fact that fat makes food delicious signifies that the Body of Christ takes away four afflictions: ignorance, weakness, malice, and concupiscence. Asher’s bread prefigures the Bread which transforms a person into Christ. As fat enables leather to stretch, so the Eucharist extends the receiver in love of neighbour. As it causes a fire to flare up, so the Body of Christ excites the soul to devotion in four ways: rightness of intention, the habit of prayer, the devotion of communion, and the habit of giving thanks.

The second figure is bread, and is developed through a consideration of the Prophet Elijah—at this time considered the

⁶⁵ 7.16.10; SAINT AUGUSTINE, *The Confessions*, trans. Maria Boulding (New York: New City Press, 1997), 127.

⁶⁶ MIRI RUBIN, *Corpus Christi: The Eucharist in Late Medieval Culture* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1991), 27–28.

⁶⁷ Conrad himself notes that four is the number of the gospels (§31), but in medieval number symbolism it also stood for the winds, elements, seasons, stages of life, corners of the world, rivers of paradise, and more; cf. ISIDORE OF SEVILLE, *Liber numerorum quae in sanctis scripturis occurrunt* 5, PL 83:183A-184A. Hopper adds that four stands for the extremities of the cross, and that it represents the earth and solidity; VINCENT HOPPER, *Medieval Number Symbolism: Its Meaning and Influence on Thought and Expression*, Columbia University Studies in English and Comparative Literature, no. 132 (New York: Columbia University Press, 1938), 84, 11, 35.

founder of the Carmelites⁶⁸—who receives bread baked under hot ashes⁶⁹ and a jug of water from an angel to sustain him in his journey to Horeb (1 Kings 19:6).⁷⁰ The eucharistic Body of Christ is truly “under ashes” since it is concealed under the accidents of bread; the water signifies the blood of Christ; the angel signifies that the Eucharist is attended by the choirs of angels. Elijah has to do four things before consuming this bread: send away his servant, enter the desert, sit under a juniper tree, and have an angel as his consoler. These signify that four things are necessary to approach the sacrament worthily: to flee the delights of the world, to enter religious life, to live under a superior, and to receive the grace of God. There are four effects: to be encouraged to action in the spirit of the commandments (the walk to Horeb), to be lifted up to contemplation which enlightens the intellect and inflames the affections (as Moses met God on the mountain), to be disposed to the revelation of divine mysteries in peace of conscience (as Elijah on Horeb), to prefer heavenly to worldly goods (as Elijah covered his face with his cloak when he saw the immensity of the divine beauty).

The third figure is honey.⁷¹ After some references to Jesus as honey and sweetness from the hymn *Iesu dulcis memoria* and to the Virgin Mary as a bee, Conrad takes up the story of Jonathan finding honey and eating it in 1 Samuel 14:27: “He put forth the end of the staff which he had in his hand, and dipped it in a honeycomb; and he carried his hand to his mouth, and his eyes were enlightened”. Jonathan did four things before he tasted the honey: he climbed laboriously on his hands and feet, made the army of the Philistines

⁶⁸ From the large literature see esp. SAGGI, “Agiografia carmelitana” in LUDOVICO SAGGI, ed., *Santi del Carmelo: biografie da vari dizionari* (Roma: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1972), 23-91; and TARCISIO STRAMARE, et al., “Elia Profeta”, *ibid.*, 136-153.

⁶⁹ As is often the case, modern translations from the Hebrew—“baked on hot coals”, “baked on hot stones”—will mislead the reader of medieval interpretations based on the Vulgate. Here *subcinericius* (“under hot ashes”) is a crucial element of Conrad’s interpretation.

⁷⁰ HEIN BLOMMESTIJN has written two interpretive essays on the Elijah section of Conrad’s sermon from the Hague ms.: “De Eucharistie”, 39-73; “De reis naar de bron: Koenraad van St. Joris,” in *Gaan waar geen weg meer is: verkenningen in de mystiek*, ed. HEIN BLOMMESTIJN (Zoetermeer: Meinema, 2002), 9-27. Cf. also Astell, *Eating Beauty*, 131-32.

⁷¹ An extensive analysis of this figure from the Tilburg ms. is by JOS HULS, “Conrad’s Allegorical Reading of 1 Samuel 14: An Analysis of a Sermon by Conrad of Saint George on the Worthy Reception of the Blessed Sacrament,” *Acta Theologica* Suppl. 15 (2011): 200-219. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/actat.v31i1S.12> (retrieved 5 June 2021).

flee, held his staff in his hand, and raised his hand to his mouth. So must the worthy recipient of the Body of Christ do four things: have a great desire to grow into virtue by daily spiritual practice, put temptation to flight, have the patronage of the Blessed Virgin Mary who bore for us the body of the Lord, and labour in good works. The effects of grace are fourfold: by frequenting the eucharist daily the mind is enlightened to know the supreme truth (Jonathan's eyes were enlightened); the experience of divine sweetness turns desire from the earthly to the divine and increases the capacity for it (he tastes the honey); the battle against evil is strengthened (he chases the Philistines as far as Aijalon); and the mortification of the outer self vivifies the inner self and extinguishes earthly desire (he says, Behold, I must die).

It is in this section that Conrad makes reference to the role of the Virgin Mary in the Christian life. Jesus is the honey produced by Mary, the bee: he is the fruit of her womb, who is the humblest among the saints. She is symbolised also by Jonathan's supporting staff, for she who bore the Lord in her body assists whoever receives the same Lord in the Eucharist. Although brief, these mentions of Mary are significant in the way that Miri Rubin has illustrated, by bringing two large contemporary theological themes into connection: "The overarching symbol of salvation, the Eucharist, was combined with another source of comfort, solace and healing, Mary, in an intersection of discourses".⁷²

The fourth figure is the paschal lamb of Exodus 12 (and also the lamb of Isaiah 16:1 and John 1:29), which signifies how the Christian must be before, during, and after reception of the Body of Christ. Before it, four things are necessary: respect for the whole community of the Church (*universitas*); a suitable disposition; charity; and integrity of faith. Four more qualities are required in one approaching the sacrament: bodily continence, purity of feeling, the memory of Christ's passion, and a desire for eternal life—each supported by allegorical interpretations of biblical verses. And there are four fruits of the sacrament: it sends consolation (God passes over Egypt); it reduces the kindling of the vices (God strikes the first-born of the Egyptians); it removes the love of the world (God judges the gods of Egypt); it makes safe in the day of judgement (the blood on your houses is a safeguard).

⁷² RUBIN, *Corpus Christi*, 140.

The fifth figure is heavenly treasure, the “hidden treasures” of Isaiah 45:3, which are hidden indeed in the sacrament. There are four of them: essence, wisdom, grace, and glory, all realised in Christ. These treasures are hidden in the bread and wine for four reasons: for the merit of faith (for eucharistic belief is opposed by the five senses, the imagination, and reason); the involvement of digestion (the horror of eating flesh); the imperfection of our senses (for as Moses could not see the face of God, so Christ is veiled in the sacrament); and the exclusion of non-believers (for the unworthy may not approach).

The sixth and final figure is the manna of Exodus 16 and the “food of angels” of Wisdom 16:20, in which we see that the sacrament of the Body of Christ is most noble in kind, sweetest in taste, most worthy in content, and marvellous in efficacy. It is the most noble food, cooked by the Trinity in the oven of the Virgin Mary by the fire of the Spirit; the sweetest, because it attracts the desire of both angels and humans; the most worthy in content, for it contains the whole of the Trinity (the Son by incarnation, and Father and Holy Spirit by the indivisibility of their substance); and marvellous in its efficacy, for the one who approaches the sacrament with an unworthy heart is only hardened in its fire, but the one who comes with charity of heart is melted. Four more commitments are required: to leave the darkness of vice (the Hebrews fled Egypt); to grow the fruit of penitence (to cross the Red Sea); to forsake earthly things—the love of possessions, the desires of the flesh, the greed for prestige—(to enter the desert); to delight in the bitterness of one’s cross and have in mind the Lord’s passion (the bitter waters of Marah, sweetened by wood).

The sermon concludes with a summary addressed directly to the listener or reader:

If you feel that you are empty, seek your fill in this sacrament under the figure of fat; if you feel hungry, seek your refreshment in this sacrament under the figure of bread; if you feel that you are sitting in darkness, seek your enlightenment in this sacrament under the figure of honey; if you see yourself lying in the shadow of death, seek your reconciliation in this sacrament under the figure of the paschal lamb; if you know yourself destitute and poor, seek your enrichment in this sacrament under the figure of heavenly treasure; if you experience yourself as having a heart of iron, seek your softening in this sacrament under the figure of manna. May Christ deign to grant it, who with the Father and the Holy Spirit lives and reigns for ever and ever. Amen.

Among others Conrad explicitly quotes Bernard of Clairvaux, Augustine, and Gregory the Great, and Jerome and Isidore for

etymologies, with implicit quotations, as it seems, from Bonaventure, Peter Lombard, Hugh of Saint Victor, Thomas of Perseigne, Thomas Aquinas, and others. However, for the most part his work reveals an original and creative mind not highly dependent on the works of others, no doubt part of the reason it was so long attributed to Bonaventure.

Hein Blommestijn has addressed the issue of whether Conrad's sermon may be called a mystical text, since he does not describe extraordinary mystical experiences nor suggest an itinerary of the mystical way.⁷³ I think that Blommestijn perhaps underestimates the mystical language in Conrad's sermon, even in the Elijah section on which he has commented: for example, the prefigured eucharistic bread which Elijah receives from the angel "lifts him up to divine contemplation" and to "the revelation of divine mysteries", and sustains him in the journey to Horeb, where he must cover his face before "the immensity of beauty and the infinity of the divine Godhead" (§32-34). In addition there are the dynamics of desire in the section on Jonathan's honey (§44). Nevertheless, his main point remains valid:

[Conrad] speaks of the "ordinary" Christian experience, which in the communion with Scripture and Eucharist arrives at the encounter with God. For him, the regular reception of the sacrament in the Eucharist is unmistakably a mystical event for the human being who opens himself fully to the love of God... The Carmelite tradition has never regarded mysticism as a "special experience" intended only for a small elite of "specialists", but always as the breakthrough of the perspective of divine love into the daily reality of every Christian who opens himself to it... Thus monasticism and lay spirituality merge into a mysticism of ordinary life... Conrad of Saint George, by means of a biblical paraphrase, interpreted the reception of the Eucharist as a mystical journey that transforms us in God's love. This gave him the opportunity to interpret the original spirituality of Carmel in a creative way in the new context of Western Europe. The contact with Eucharistic mysticism

⁷³ For critique of William James' experientialism, which has so dominated the modern conception of mysticism, see, for example, EDWARD HOWELLS, "Mystical Theology and Human Experience," in *Oxford Handbook of Mystical Theology*, ed. EDWARD HOWELLS and MARK A. MCINTOSH (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2020), 45–64, with further bibliography; JONATHAN GARB, "Mystics' Critiques of Mystical Experience," *Revue de l'Histoire des Religions* 221/223 (2004): 293–325; RALPH NORMAN, "Rediscovery of Mysticism," in *The Blackwell Companion to Modern Theology*, ed. GARETH JONES, Blackwell Companions to Religion (Oxford: Blackwell, 2004), 449–65.

from the thirteenth century, which was characteristic of the Northern European women's movement, will certainly not have been a stranger to this.⁷⁴

All in all, then, Conrad's sermon may be considered the first known mystical work by a Carmelite author.

The present edition

The Quaracchi editors knew sixteen manuscripts, and used five in their edition, all of them from the Bavarian State Library. None bears Conrad's name; seven of the sixteen are attributed to Bonaventure. A critical edition would no doubt be a valuable undertaking, but I must leave it to another. It would be a fairly large task, as there are some forty-five known manuscripts, and no doubt others to be discovered. The presence of the work in late medieval miscellany manuscripts, which are not always fully catalogued, is likely to complicate the manuscript survey, as is the possibility that the work was transmitted in various partial forms. A comparison with the vernacular versions would also be of value.

In the meantime, it seems worthwhile to present Conrad's sermon in a transcription from the Paris manuscript, Bibliothèque Mazarine, ms. 987, ff. 46v-57r, the only known version of the Latin text to bear his name. This manuscript is a miscellany, dated 1397, of different documents on the Eucharist, containing four sermons, ten exempla, and twenty-three small treatises or chapters of treatises, written in two hands.⁷⁵ It was copied at the priory of Augustinian canons at Groenendaal in the forest of Zonien in Flemish Brabant, which had been founded in 1343 by John Ruusbroec and two others, and is further evidence for the long-lasting interest in Conrad's sermon among followers of Ruusbroec.⁷⁶ In the Mazarine manuscript the work is under the title *Sermo fratris Conradi*⁷⁷ *de sancto Georgio*,

⁷⁴ BLOMMESTIJN, "De Eucharistie," 72-73.

⁷⁵ BOUGEROL, "Le manuscrit Paris Mazarine 987," 7-8.

⁷⁶ A note on a flyleaf reads: "Liber cenobii Sancti Pauli in Zonia, quod communiter vocatur Roodendale, dirigatur illac." On the Groenendaal priory cf. JOHN ARBLASTER and ROB FAESEN, "John of Ruusbroec's Life and Works," in *A Companion to John of Ruusbroec*, ed. JOHN ARBLASTER and ROB FAESEN, Brill's Companions to the Christian Tradition, vol. 51 (Leiden: Brill, 2014), 47-81.

⁷⁷ Not "Corradi", as transcribed by BOUGEROL in "Le manuscrit Paris Mazarine 987," 6; and SAINT BONAVENTURE, *Sermons de Diversis*, 50.

nacione Coloniensi, ordinis fratrum beate Marie de Monte Carmelo, de sacramento altaris, but the more common title *De corpore Christi* in used in the explicit. The latter seems to better reflect Conrad's characteristic vocabulary,⁷⁸ and I have continued to use it as the title of the sermon.

Bougerol has given a meticulous analysis of the contents of the manuscript, which it is not necessary to repeat here.⁷⁹ The large majority of the constitutive elements, some very brief, are by unidentified authors, but there are extracts from Bonaventure's *Breviloquium*, Thomas of Cantimpré's *De apibus*, Henry Suso's *Horologium sapientiae*, Albert the Great's *Summa de corpore Domini*, and the bull of Urban IV establishing the feast of Corpus Christi, along with a number of *exempla* of the kind used in preaching.

I have collated the text with that of the Quaracchi edition, which in turn collated five Bavarian manuscripts with the 1774 edition of Bonelli.⁸⁰ This is admittedly not an ideal procedure, since the variants in the *apparatus criticus* below are not drawn from manuscripts but rather from the 1891 edition, which itself is not ideal.⁸¹ Moreover, the discursive 19th-century Quaracchi apparatus makes it difficult to disentangle the manuscripts from which particular readings are taken—a disentangling which I have not attempted. In addition, it seems that the Franciscan editors have introduced unsupported readings in an attempt to correct the medieval Latin to a more classical standard, and have regularly conformed biblical quotations to the Vulgate. This collation is nevertheless presented as a worthwhile interim measure, to draw attention to the existence of this important early Carmelite text in a particular manuscript, while enabling some corrections to the far-from-perfect Mazarine text and especially the supplying of some omissions. A more thorough job can be done if there is an eventual critical edition which takes account of the other surviving manuscripts.

⁷⁸ Apart from the scribal title *De sacramento altaris*, variants of *sacramentum altaris* are only found four times in the text, while variants of *corpus Christi* occur twenty-nine times.

⁷⁹ BOUGEROL, "Le manuscrit Paris Mazarine 987," 8–17.

⁸⁰ The mss. are: Munich, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek Clm 9612, 9598, 2657, 7012, 9617; "Prolegomena", xlvi.

⁸¹ For some critical comments on the Quaracchi edition see BRADY, "The Opera Omnia of St. Bonaventure Revisited"; JACQUES GUY BOUGEROL, "Pour des 'Prolegomena postquam' de l'édition critique de s. Bonaventure Quaracchi 1882–1902," in *The Editing of Theological and Philosophical Texts from the Middle Ages*, ed. MÓNICA ASZTALOS, *Studia Latina Stockholmiensia*, vol. 30 (Stockholm: Almqvist and Wiksell, 1986), 121–35.

I have worked from a digital copy provided by the Bibliothèque Mazarine. Bougerol makes a somewhat strange comment that the texts of the Mazarine manuscript and the edition in Bonaventure's *opera* are exactly the same "de la première lettre à la dernière",⁸² though there are in fact a large number of variants, including some omissions from the former. *M* indicates the Mazarine manuscript, and *q* the Quaracchi edition. I have preserved the text of *M* as far as possible, except where it is clearly incorrect or lacking. Emendations and additions in the text (almost always from *q*) are indicated by angle brackets <>; other variants are in the apparatus. I have preserved the orthography of the manuscript, regularising u and v to u, and capitalising, punctuating and paragraphing according to the sense. I have consistently written the soft or assibilated -t- as -c-, as is the scribe's usual practice, even if occasionally it seems it may have been written as -t-. I have not recorded trivial variants (is/ille/iste, iuxta/secundum, aut/sive, presence or absence of et, etc., or simple inversions of word order). To avoid very frequent repetition I have not generally indicated that variants in biblical quotations often result from the Quaracchi practice of conforming such quotations to the standard Vulgate text; this can be presumed.⁸³ Folio changes in *M* are indicated [f. 47r] and page changes in *q* [p. 555] and so on.

M has been lightly corrected by the original scribe and occasionally by a later hand, e.g. on f. 47r, where an incorrect rubric has been corrected in black ink. There are occasional *nota* annotations in the margins, which have been recorded in the apparatus, and some annotations of structural elements (1°, 2°, etc.), also recorded, although some have apparently been lost through later trimming.

The Quaracchi editors divided this 7000-word sermon into 42 numbered sections, but a more granular division seems useful, so for ease of reference I have indicated the six main sections I-VI, and numbered the paragraphs 1-90.

An English translation is in preparation.

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⁸² BOUGEROL, "Le manuscrit Paris Mazarine 987," 6.

⁸³ I have used the Clementine Vulgate, which, though published in 1592, closely corresponds to the 13th-century Paris text commonly used throughout the Middle Ages; cf. JEAN LONGÈRE, *La prédication médiévale* (Paris: Etudes Augustiniennes, 1983), 180; *Biblia sacra iuxta Vulgatam Clementinam*, 6th ed., ed. A. COLUNGA and L. TURRADO, Biblioteca de Autores Cristianos (Madrid: La Editorial Católica, 1982).

SIGLA

- M* Paris, Bibliotheque Mazarine, Ms 987, ff. 46v-57r
q St Bonaventure, *Doctoris seraphici S. Bonaventurae ... opera omnia*, tomus V, Opuscula varia theologica, Quaracchi: ex typographia Collegii S. Bonaventurae, 1891, 553-566.

Sermo fratris Conradi de Sancto Georgio natione coloniensi ordinis fratrum beate marie de monte carmeli. De sacramento altaris.¹ [p. 554]

1. *Confiteantur Domino misericordie eius, et mirabilia eius filiis hominum; quia saciavit animam inanem atque animam esurientem saciavit bonis, sedentem in tenebris et umbra mortis, vinctum² in mendicitate et ferro.³* Istud verbum scribit David Propheta, in quo uerbo³ excitat nos ad graciaram acciones, cum dicit: *Confiteantur*,⁴ et cetera,⁵ et ad rationem graciaram accionis, cum subdit:⁶ *Quia saciauit animam inanem*,⁷ et cetera.

2. Volens ergo Propheta corda nostra excitare ad graciaram acciones, ostendit multiplices nostre miserie defectus;⁸ ostendit⁹ hic eiam multiplices effectus diuine misericordie. Dicit enim hic, quia homo inanis erat, homo esuriebat, homo in tenebris sedebat, in umbra mortis iacebat, uinctus in mendicitate et ferro. Inanis erat anima,¹⁰ quia non habebat spiritum Dei¹¹ in se per inhabitationem. Esuriebat, quia non habebat spiritualem refeccionem. In tenebris sedebat, quia

¹ Sermo... altaris] *rub. M* : De sanctissimo corpore Christi *q*

² sedentem; vinctum] sedentes; vinctos *ut Vulg. q*

³ uerbo] *om. q*

⁴ Confiteantur] *add. Domino q*

⁵ ecc.] *add. M sup. l.*

⁶ et ad... subdit] Subiungit rationem cum dicit *q*

⁷ animam inanem] *om. q*

⁸ ostendit multiplices... effectus] ostendit in hoc verbo defectus nostrae miseriae, nihilominus multiplices effectus *q*

⁹ Ostendit] Dicit enim *q*

¹⁰ anima] *om. q*

¹¹ spiritum Dei] Deum *q*

^a Confiteantur... ferro] Ps. 106, 8-10.

non habebat diuinam cognicionem. In umbra mortis iacebat, quia iudicata erat in dampnacionem. Vinctus erat in mendicitate, quia non habebat virtuosam operacionem. Vinctus erat ferro, quia habebat cordis obstinacionem.

3. *Confiteantur ergo Domino misericordie eius*, et cetera, quia¹² repleuit inanem, saciauit esurientem, illuminauit in tenebris sedentem, reconciliauit in umbra mortis iacentem, ditauit mendicantem, mellificauit¹³ ferreum cor habentem.

4. Homo erat inanis, et ipse se dedit ei per inhabitationem. Homo esuriebat, et ipse se dedit ei per refeccionem. In tenebris sedebat, et ipse dedit ei se in cordis illuminacionem. In umbra mortis iacebat, et ipse dedit se ei per¹⁴ reconciliacionis oblacionem. Homo [f. 47r] vinctus erat in mendicitate, et ipse se dedit ei in uirtuosam operacionem. Vinctus erat ferro, id est corde obstinato, et ipse se dedit ei in cordis mollificacionem. *Confiteantur Domino misericordie eius*, etc., quia replecio est¹⁵ inanium, refeccio esurientium, lumen in tenebris sedentium, reconciliacio in umbra mortis iacencium, ditacio mendicantium, et mollificacio ferreorum cordium. Hec omnia tanguntur in uerbis thematis, sicut patet.

5. Et propter hec sex sub sex figuris prefiguratur¹⁶ corpus Christi in scripturis, videlicet sub figura adipis,¹⁷ sub figura panis, sub figura mellis, sub figura agni paschalis, sub figura thesauri celestis, et sub figura manatis.

6. Quia ergo pinguedo est quid penetratiuum, ideo ualet ad replecionem inanium, quoad primum. Quia panis est quid fortificatiuum, ideo ualet ad refeccionem esurientium, quoad secundum. Quia mel oculorum est purificatiuum, ideo ualet ad illuminacionem in tenebris sedencium, quoad tercium. Quia agnus¹⁸ est aliquid immolatiuum, ideo ualet ad reconciliacionem in umbra mortis iacencium, quoad quartum. Quia thesaurus est quid desideratiuum, ideo ualet ad ditacionem mendicantium, quoad quintum. Quia ergo¹⁹ manna est quid liquefactiuum, ideo ualet ad mollificacionem ferreorum cordium, quoad sextum.²⁰

¹² quia] *add.* ipse *q*

¹³ mellicauit] mollivit *q*

¹⁴ per] in *q*

¹⁵ est] ipse est *q*

¹⁶ prefiguratur] praefiguratum est *q*

¹⁷ adipis] *add.* sive pinguedinis *q*

¹⁸ agnus] *add.* paschalis *q*

¹⁹ ergo] *om.* *q*

²⁰ post sextum] *add. et canc. rub.* De sacramento sermo et *add. in marg. manu altera* De figura pinguedinis *M : om. q*

<I.> *De figura pinguedinis*

7. *Confiteantur domino misericordie eius et mirabilia eius filiis hominum*, quia¹ prefiguravit² nobis corpus suum³ sanctissimum sub figura pinguedinis, et hoc recte. Corpus enim Christi datum est nobis ad conseruandum diuinum feruorem in corde; qui conseruatur tripliciter: scilicet,⁴ per delectacionem intra semetipsum, per dileccionem ad proximum, et per deuocionem ad Deum.

8. Delectacio autem intra semetipsum non habetur nisi per uiaticum refeccionis; dileccio ad proximum habetur per sacramentum communionis; deuocio ad Deum⁵ per sacrificium oblacionis. Et ideo ad hec tria datum est corpus Christi, uidelicet in uiaticum refeccionis, ut conseruet delectacionem intra semetipsum; in sacramentum communionis, ut conseruet dileccionem ad proximum; et in sacrificium oblacionis, ut conseruet deuocionem ad Deum. Et hec tria facit pinguedo:⁶ delectabiles [p. 555] enim reddit quos [f. 47v] infundit cibos,⁷ quoad primum; dilatat pellem quam perungit, quoad secundum; flammam subleuat quam attingit, quoad tertium.

9. Quia ergo pinguedo delectabiles reddit cibos, figurat⁸ corpus Christi, quod et magnam delectacionem homini facit intra semetipsum, qui illud deuote comedit. Sed⁹ hoc figuratum est Genesis penultimo: *Aser; pinguis panis eius, delicias prebens*¹⁰ *regibus*.^a Iste panis magnas delicias homini infundit, quia tollit omne quod affligit.

10. Quatuor sunt enim que affligunt hominem in hac uita, scilicet ignorancia, impotencia, malicia¹¹ et concupiscencia; et hec quatuor inflictas sunt homini propter originale peccatum. Unde Psalmi-

¹ Quia] *praem.* Primo *q*

² prefiguravit] *praefiguratur q*

³ suum] Christi *q*

⁴ scilicet] *om. q*

⁵ Deum] *add.* habetur *q*

⁶ pinguedo] *add.* sub figura *M*

⁷ reddit... cibos] facit cibos quos infundit *q*

⁸ figurat] significat *q*

⁹ Sed] *Et q*

¹⁰ prebens] et praebebit *q*

¹¹ malicia] *add. in marg. altera manu M*

^a Gen. 49, 20

sta,¹² *Afflictus sum et humiliatus sum nimis*, et statim subiungit:¹³ *Dereliquit me uirtus mea*, quantum ad impotentiam; *et lumen oculorum meorum non est mecum*, quantum <ad>¹⁴ ignorantiam; *amici mei et proximi mei aduersum me appropinquauerunt*,^{15b} quantum ad¹⁶ concupiscenciam. Amicos enim et proximos uocat carnem cum concupiscenciis, et tamen eos patitur¹⁷ aduersarios, quia *caro concupiscit aduersus spiritum*,^{18c} *et qui iuxta me erant de longe steterunt*,^d id est angeli,¹⁹ <quoad>²⁰ maliciam.

11. Contra hec quatuor in premissis uerbo datur corpus Christi sub figura panis.

12. *Aser*, <panis>²¹ *pinguis, delicias prebens*, et panis regum dicitur. Panis regum dicitur quia, confortando reges, facit contra impotentiam, ut scilicet *rex*, id est ratio recta, *sedens in solio*,²² id est in gubernaculo²³ anime,ⁱ *dissipet enim omne malum intuitu suo*.^{24e} Dicitur etiam corpus Christi panis pinguis, quia illuminat contra ignorantiam. Pinguedo enim in testa posita vel infusa lampadi dat usum luminis. Dicitur etiam panis *delicias prebens* contra carnis concupiscencias. Iste enim est panis *habens in se*²⁵ *omne delectamentum et omnis saporis*

¹² Psalmista] Psalmus *q*

¹³ subiungit] *add.* causam dicens *q*

¹⁴ ad] *add.* *ex q* : *om. M*

¹⁵ appropinquauerunt] *add.* et steterunt *q*

¹⁶ quantum ad] quoad *q*

¹⁷ patitur] *om. q*

¹⁸ spiritum] *add.* ad Galatos quinto *q*

¹⁹ id est angeli] *om. q*

²⁰ quoad] *corr.* *ex q* : propter *M*

²¹ panis] *add.* *ex q* : *om. M*

²² solio] *add.* iudicii *q*

²³ gubernaculo] gubernatione recta *q*

²⁴ intuitu suo] *add.* sicut dicitur in Proverbiis *q*

²⁵ in se] *om. q*

^b Afflictus... appropinquauerunt] cfr Ps. 37, 9, 11-12

^c caro... spiritum] Gal. 5, 17

^d et qui... steterunt] Ps 37, 12

^e rex... suo] cfr Prov. 20, 8

ⁱ gubernaculo anime] cfr AMBROSIIUS MEDIOLANENSIS, *Expositio psalmi CXVIII* 4.7.2; ed. Petschenig, CSEL 62:70; PL 15:1243A

suauitatem.^{26f} Dicitur eciam *panis Aser*, qui interpretatur 'beatitudo',ⁱⁱ quia totum hominem beatificat contra²⁷ maliciam. Virtus enim huius panis est, ut transmutet hominem in Christum, qui summe beatus est per essenciam, beatificans alios per gratiam. Unde Dominus²⁸ ad beatum Augustinum: 'Non tu mutabis me in te, sicut cibum carnis tue, sed tu mutaberis in me'.ⁱⁱⁱ

13. Secundo, datum est corpus Christi in sacramentum communionis ad conseruandam dileccionem ad proximum; et ideo bene significatur per pinguedinem. Sicut enim pinguedo dilatat pellem, quam perungit, sic corpus Christi dilatat [f. 48r] animam, que ipsum deuote sumit.²⁹ Dilatat autem ad omnem partem posicionis, uidelicet supra et infra, ad dexteram et sinistram, ante et retro; et propter hoc dicitur Iheremie trigesimo sexto: *Inebriabo animas*³⁰ *sacerdotum pinguedine*.^g

14. Pinguedinem, qua animas³¹ sacerdotum inebriat, uocat hic sacramentum altaris, quo animas esuriencium digne <sumencium>³² ad caritatem inflammat, que animam uehementer ad omnem posicionem dilatat; et propter hoc subiungit,³³ *Et populus meus bonis meis adimplebitur*.^h Populum hic uocat totam ecclesiam, tam militantem quam triumphantem.

15. Postquam³⁴ anima sacerdotis enim fuerit inebriata³⁵ ex huius sacramenti uirtute dileccionis³⁶ pinguedine, statim replet totam eccle-

²⁶ *suauitatem]* *add.* Sapientiae decimo sexto *q*

²⁷ *contra]* *add.* omnem *q*

²⁸ *Dominus]* *add.* dixit *q*

²⁹ *sumit]* comedit *q*

³⁰ *animas]* animam *q*

³¹ *animas]* animam *bis q*

³² *sumencium]* *add.* *ex q : om. M*

³³ *subiungit]* subiungitur *q*

³⁴ *Postquam]* *add in marg.* nota *M*

³⁵ *inebriata]* *add. in marg.* nota *M*

³⁶ *ex... dileccionis]* ex huius uisione Sacramenti *q*

^f omne... *suauitatem]* cfr Sap. 16, 20

^g *inebriabo... pinguedine]* Ier. 31, 14

^h *Et... implebitur]* Ier. 31, 14

ⁱⁱ qui... *beatitudo]* RABANUS MAURUS, *Commentaria in librum Iudicum* 1.13; PL 108:1147A

ⁱⁱⁱ non tu... *in me]* AUGUSTINUS HIPPONENSIS, *Confessiones* 7.10.16; ed. Verheijen, CCSL 27:103–104; PL 32:742.

siam bonis, quia³⁷ ex habundancia caritatis dilatatur supra³⁸ in celum, offerendo ad honorem regnancium;³⁹ dilatatur infra usque ad purgatorium, quia offert pro redempcione ibidem existencium; dilatatur ad <dexteram>,⁴⁰ quia offertur⁴¹ pro salute amicorum et benefactorum; dilatatur ad sinistram, quia offertur pro salute inimicorum et persecutorum; dilatatur retro, quia offert pro salute antecessorum suorum; dilatatur⁴² ante, quia offert pro salute omnium predestinatorum usque ad diem iudicii futurorum.

16. Tercio eciam datum est nobis corpus Christi in sacrificium oblacionis, ut conseruet deuocionem ad Deum; et ideo figuratum⁴³ est bene in pinguedine, [p. 556] quia sicut pinguedo igni superfusa subleuat flammam in altum, sic diuinissima eucharistia, a deuoto corde percepta,⁴⁴ rapit ipsum per deuocionem ad Deum. Et propter hoc in psalmo dicitur, *In nomine tuo levabo manus meas. Sicut adipe et pinguedine repleatur anima mea, et labiis exsultacionis laudabit os meum.*ⁱ Sicut enim uas repletum adipe et pinguedine, non ualet se⁴⁵ continere interius, nisi desudat⁴⁶ exterius, sic corpus Christi, cum animam repleuerit interius⁴⁷ pinguedine deuocionis, eructat exterius in labiis exsultacionis.

17. Tanguntur autem quatuor in isto verbo,⁴⁸ que solent conseruare deuocionem ad Deum, uidelicet rectitudo intencionis, consuetudo oracionis, deuocio communionis, et consuetudo⁴⁹ graciaram accionis. Et ista ita ordinate debent fieri, quod primo homo⁵⁰ preparet rectam intencionem, postea se ipsum [f. 48v] excitet per oracionem, ac

³⁷ quia] *om. q*

³⁸ supra] usque *q*

³⁹ offerendo... regnancium] offerendo Deo ad honorem Sanctorum in caelo regnantium *q*

⁴⁰ dexteram] *corr. ex q* : proximum *M*

⁴¹ offertur] offert *bis q*

⁴² dilatur] *om. q*

⁴³ figuratum] significatum *q*

⁴⁴ percepta] suscepta *q*

⁴⁵ ualet se] valens *q*

⁴⁶ nisi desudat] redundat *q*

⁴⁷ interius] *om. q*

⁴⁸ uerbo] *add. in marg. nota M*

⁴⁹ consuetudo] consecutio *q*

⁵⁰ ita...homo] et istud debet ita ordinare homo, quod primo *q*

ⁱ In nomine... meum] Ps. 62, 5-6.

postea⁵¹ deuote accedat ad communionem, et tunc exultatio⁵² resoluat os ad graciaram accionem.

18. Primo enim debet habere intencionem rectam,⁵³ quia non debet offerre⁵⁴ sacrificium hoc propter fauorem humanum et⁵⁵ propter carnale commodum aut propter lucrum temporalium, sed⁵⁶ propter honorem diuinum, propter utilitatem proximorum, et augmentum suorum meritorum. Et propter hoc dicitur, *In nomine tuo, iuxta illud Apostoli, quidquid facitis siue in uerbo siue in opere, omnia in nomine Domini nostri Iesu Christi facite.*^j

19. Debet etiam accedens ad hoc sacramentum excitatus ad deuocionem esse.⁵⁷ Et propter hoc dicitur: *Leuabo manus meas,*^k uide licet per deuotam⁵⁸ oracionem, iuxta illud Apostoli ad Tymotheum: *Volo uiros in omni loco orare, leuantes puras manus*^l ad Deum.⁵⁹ Et sic contritus ac⁶⁰ deuotus debet accedere ad communionem; et propter hoc⁶¹ subditur: *Sicut adype et pinguedine repleatur anima mea.*^m

20. Et⁶² impinguatus per deuocionem et inflammatus per dileccionem, debet erumpere in graciaram accionem. Et propter hoc⁶³ subiungitur: *Et labiis exultacionis laudabit os meum.*ⁿ

21. *Confiteantur Domino misericordie eius* et cetera, quia prefigurauit nobis sanctissimum⁶⁴ corpus suum in figura pinguedinis.

Explicit de pinguedine.

⁵¹ ac postea] et ex tunc q

⁵² tunc exultatio] ultimo q

⁵³ rectam] *add. in marg. nota M*

⁵⁴ offerre] *add. homo q*

⁵⁵ humanum et] hominum vel q

⁵⁶ sed] *add. pure q*

⁵⁷ esse] *om., et add. non enim tepido corde debet aliquis accedere, quia sic mereri posset obstinationem q*

⁵⁸ deuotam] *om. q*

⁵⁹ ad Deum] scilicet ad Dominum q

⁶⁰ contritus ac] tertio q

⁶¹ et... hoc] unde q

⁶² Et] *add. ultimo q*

⁶³ et... hoc] ideo q

⁶⁴ sanctissimum] primo q

^j Quidquid... facite] cfr Col. 3, 17.

^k Leuabo... meas] Ps. 62, 5.

^l Volo... Deum] 1 Tim. 2, 8

^m sicut adype... mea] Ps. 62, 6.

ⁿ et labiis... os meum] Ps. 62, 6.

<II.> *Incipit de figura panis*¹

22. Secundo prefiguravit nobis hoc sacratissimum corpus suum sub figura² panis. Iste est panis de quo dicitur,³ *Ego sum panis uiuus*,^a et cetera.⁴ Item ibidem: *Panis quem ego dedero*,⁵ *caro mea est*,^b et cetera.⁶

23. Iste est panis, quem attulit angelus Helye, sicut dicitur tercii Regum xviii:⁷ *Surrexit*⁸ *Elias, et ecce ad caput eius subcinericius panis et uas aque*.^c Panis subcinericius est corpus Christi, qui bene dicitur subcinericius, quia uelatur accidentibus. Per cineres enim significantur accidentia, et sub illis accidentibus cinerum⁹ latet refeccio nostrarum mencium. Quod autem dicitur, erat ibi *uas aque*, hoc additur propter sanguinis Christi mysterium.

24. Quod autem iste panis allatus est per angelicum ministerium, significat cum conficitur hoc sacramentum, ibi¹⁰ adest magnus exercitus angelorum. Unde¹¹ Gregorius¹² [f. 49r]: 'Cui fidelium dubium est, ipsa immolacionis hora ad uocem¹³ sacerdotis celos aperiri, yma summis sociari, siue coequari,¹⁴ terrestria¹⁵ celestibus iungi, unumque ex uisibilibus inuisibiliter¹⁶ fieri? Sed cum hoc¹⁷ agimus, necesse est, ut prius coram Deo¹⁸ in compuncione in cordis ara¹⁹ mactemus.'¹

¹ explicit... panis] *rub. M : om. q*

² sub figura] in forma *q*

³ Iste... dicitur] De quo ipse dicit Ioannis sexto *q*

⁴ et cetera] qui de caelo descendi *q*.

⁵ dedero] dabo *q*

⁶ et cetera] pro mundi vita *q*

⁷ xviii] decimo nono *recte q*

⁸ Surrexit] Respexit *ut Vulg. q*

⁹ accidentibus cinerum] cineribus accidentium *q*

¹⁰ ibi] *fort. ubi M*

¹¹ Unde] *om. q*

¹² Gregorius] *add. in Dialogo q*

¹³ uocem] *add. in marg. nota M*

¹⁴ siue coequari] *om. q*

¹⁵ terrestria] *terrena q*

¹⁶ inuisibiliter] atque inuisibilibus *q*

¹⁷ hoc] *haec q*

¹⁸ deo] *add. nosmetipsos Deo q*

¹⁹ in cordis ara] *cordis in ara q*

^a ego... uiuus] Ioh. 6, 51

^b panis... mea est] Ioh. 6, 52.

ⁱ Cui... mactemus] GREGORIUS MAGNUS, *Libri dialogorum*, 4.58-59; PL 77:428A.

25. Sed priusquam iste Helyas uenit²⁰ ad huius panis refeccionem, quatuor legitur fecisse: primo²¹ quia reliquit puerum, uenit in desertum, sedit subtus unam²² iuniperum, et habuit suscitatore[m] angelum, ad significandum quod quatuor debet habere qui digne uult²³ ad hoc sacramentum accedere. Primo²⁴ debet mundi fugere consolacionem; et debet intrare religionem; et ibi debet habere²⁵ prelati subieccionem ac [p. 557] Dei deuocionem,²⁶ et hec sunt ista quatuor que supra diximus.

26. Primo ergo debet fugere mundi consolacionem. Cum enim in hoc sacramento sit plenitudo consolacionis spiritualis, et talis 'non datur²⁷ admittentibus alienam',²⁸ sicut dicit Bernardus;ⁱⁱ ideo necesse est,²⁹ qui uult attingere spiritualem consolacionem ut dimitterat carnalem delectacionem. Et hoc est quod hic dicitur, <quod *cum venisset in Bersabee, reliquit ibi puerum suum*>.^{d30} Bersabee interpretatur 'fons sacietatis'ⁱⁱⁱ et significat Christum, in quo est omnis plenitudo gratiarum. Hanc plenitudinem qui attingit omnem consolacionem³¹ mundi relinquit: et hoc est quod subiungitur:³² *Reliquit ibi puerum suum*. Quid per puerum nisi carnalem delectacionem siue oblectacionem intelligimus, quod reuera puerile est?³³ Hunc³⁴ puerum nos relinquere Aposto-

²⁰ iste Helyas uenit] Elias venerat *q*

²¹ primo] *om. q*

²² unam] *om. q*

²³ uult] *add. in marg. nota M*

²⁴ Primo] *add. in marg. 1° M*

²⁵ habere] *add. respectu q*

²⁶ ac Dei deuocionem] debet habere ad Deum deuotionem *q*

²⁷ datur] *detur q*

²⁸ alienam] *add. consolacionem q*

²⁹ est] *add. ut q*

³⁰ quod cum venisset... puerum suum] *add. ex q : om. M*

³¹ consolacionem] delectacionem *q*

³² subiungitur] *subditur q*

³³ siue... puerile est] *accipimus q*

³⁴ Hunc] *Quem q*

^c surrexit... aque] III Reg. 19, 6.

^d cum venisset... puerum suum] III Reg. 19, 3.

ⁱⁱ et talis... alienam] GAUFRIDUS CLARAEVALLENSIS, *De colloquio Simonis cum Iesu ex sermonibus Bernardi* 55.66; PL 184:472A.

ⁱⁱⁱ fons sacietatis] cfr HIERONYMUS STRIDONENSIS, *Liber interpretationis hebraicorum nominum* s.v. Bersabee, ed. Lagarde CCSL 72:62, 103; PL 23: 813A

lus docet,³⁵ cum dicebat: *Nolite pueri effici sensibus, sed malicia parvuli estote.*^e Ille ergo *relinquit puerum*, qui *relinquit puerilem modum uiuendi.*³⁶

27. Secundo³⁷ qui digne uult accedere ad hoc sacramentum debet se componere ad uitam honeste religionis.³⁸ Et hoc est quod dicitur hic, quod Elias *perrexit in desertum.*^f Desertum significat statum religiosum,^{iv} quia dicitur a deserendo:^v quia³⁹ ibi deseruntur omnia temporalia. Deseruntur eciam⁴⁰ ibi diuicie per uotum paupertatis, deliciae per uotum castitatis, honores dignitatis⁴¹ mundane per abnegacionem proprie uoluntatis. Et nichil <tam nociuum>⁴² est in mundo, quam⁴³ ista tria, sicut Iohannes in Canonica sua: *Omne quod est in mundo, aut est concupiscencia carnis, aut concupiscencia oculorum, aut superbia uite.*^g Et quia per hec tria animas peccatrices captiuat diabolus, eciam per hec tria animas religiosas impugnat: quod significatum est Deuteronomii octauo, ubi dicitur⁴⁴ quod in deserto *erat serpens flatu* [f. 49v] *adurens*, id est dyabolus temptans per superbiam; *et dypsas* siti interficiens,⁴⁵ id est dyabolus temptans per avariciam; *et scorpio* uultu blandiens et cauda pungens, id est dyabolus temptans per carnis concupiscenciam.^h

³⁵ apostolus docet] docebat Apostolus q

³⁶ modum uiuendi] mundi modum q

³⁷ Secundo] *add. in marg. 2^o M*

³⁸ vitam honeste religionis] uitae honestae religionem q

³⁹ quia] et q

⁴⁰ etiam] enim q

⁴¹ dignitatis] et dignitates q

⁴² tam nociuum] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁴³ quam] sicut q

⁴⁴ ubi dicitur] *om. q*

⁴⁵ interficiens] deficiens M

^e Nolite... estote] I Cor. 14, 20.

^f perrexit in desertum] III Reg. 19, 4.

^g Omne... uite] I Ioh. 2, 26.

^h erat serpens... scorpio] cfr Deut. 8, 15.

^{iv} Desertum... religiosum] cfr HUGO DE S. VICTORE, *De scripturis et scriptoribus sacris* 16; PL175: 23B.

^v dicitur a deserendo] cfr BEDA VENERABILIS, *In primam partem Samuhelis libri iu et Nomina locorum* 4:23, ed. Hurst, CCSL 119:220; PL 91:672C.

28. Tercio⁴⁶ debet habere respectu prelati subieccionem: et hoc est quod dicitur hic, quod Helyas *sedt subter unam iuniperum*. Iuniperus, sicut dicit Ysidorus, est arbor cuius cineres conservant ignem per totum annum.^{vi} Quid ergo significare possumus per iuniperum⁴⁷ nisi bonum prelatum? Cuius iuniperi cineres sunt⁴⁸ humilitas prelati, quae solet conseruare in pectoribus subditorum ignem mutue dileccionis et feruorem⁴⁹ ac calorem feruide deuocionis.

29. Quarto⁵⁰ debet habere respectu Dei deuocionem, et hoc est quod hic dicitur, quod angelus suscitauit eum. Quid <significatur>⁵¹ per angelum nisi diuine gracie donum? Angelus enim nuncius interpretatur.^{52vii} Tunc enim Deus ad nos quasi angelum⁵³ mittit, quando <graciam nobis immittit. Et iste angelus semel et iterum excitat, quia diuine gracie donum semper>⁵⁴ ad proficiendum nos in spiritu instigat.

30. Sed qui digne ad hoc sacramentum accedit, uacuuus non recedit. Et ideo⁵⁵ quatuor sunt,⁵⁶ que haurire solent in hoc sacramento qui digne accedunt. Hoc enim sacramentum confortat ad accionem, subleuat ad contemplacionem, disponit ad diuinorum reuelacionem, accendit⁵⁷ ad diuinorum et eternorum bonorum desideracionem.⁵⁸ Et ideo dicitur hic, quod Helyas *in fortitudine cibi illius ambulauit*,⁵⁹ ad [p. 558] *montem Dei peruenit*, secreta Dei⁶⁰ uidit, et *in ostio spelunce stetit*: et hec sunt illa quatuor.

⁴⁶ Tercio] *add. in marg. 3° M*

⁴⁷ per iuniperum] *praem. post ergo q*

⁴⁸ Cuius iuniperi cineres sunt] *Cinis iuniperi est q*

⁴⁹ feruorem ac] *om. q*

⁵⁰ Quarto] *add in marg. ut uid. 4° M*

⁵¹ significatur] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁵² nuncius interpretatur] *interpretatur nuntius q*

⁵³ ad nos quasi angelum] *quasi Angelum ad nos q*

⁵⁴ graciam nobis... semper] *add. q : om. M*

⁵⁵ ideo] *add. nota quod q*

⁵⁶ quatuor sunt] *add. in marg. nota M*

⁵⁷ accendit] *animat et accendit q*

⁵⁸ ad diuinorum... desideracionem] *ad mundi contemptum et ad caelestium aeternorumque bonorum desideracionem q*

⁵⁹ ambulauit] *add. usque q*

⁶⁰ Dei] *divina q*

^{vi} Iuniperus] *cfr ISIDORUS HISPALENSIS, Etymologiae 17.7.35; ed. Lindsay, p. 117.*

^{vii} angelus... interpretatur] *AUGUSTINUS HIPONENSIS, De ciuitate Dei 15.23; ed. Hoffman, CSEL 40.2:109; ISIDORUS HISPALENSIS, Eymologiae 6.2.43; ed. Lindsay, 72.*

31. Primum ergo quod hauritur⁶¹ in hoc sacramento quia anima deuota confortatur⁶² ad accionem, quia propter hoc⁶³ dicitur hic, *Ambulauit in fortitudine cibi illius quadraginta diebus*, et cetera.ⁱ Iste cibus significat corpus Christi, in cuius fortitudine homo laborat, dum in spirituali uita proficere⁶⁴ non cessat. *Ambulauit*⁶⁵ autem *quadraginta diebus*. In quadragenario est denarius numerus⁶⁶ per quaternarium ductus.^{viii} Per denarium significatur decalogus,^{ix} ad quem reducit totum uetus testamentum. Per quaternarium significantur quatuor Evangelia, ad quae reducit totum novum testamentum. Ambulare igitur in fortitudine cibi illius per quadraginta dies⁶⁷ est proficere in spirituali uita toto tempore nostro, quo regitur uita nostra per nouum et uetus testamentum.

32. Secundo,⁶⁸ subleuatur ad contemplacionem, et propter hoc⁶⁹ dicitur hic, quod *pervenit ad montem Dei*. Quid per montem significare possumus nisi mentis subleuacionem? Ad hunc montem perueniebat⁷⁰ Moyses,⁷¹ unde:⁷² *Moyses* [f. 50r] *pascebat oves*,^j et cetera. Ibi notatur exercitium accionis. Postea *minauit gregem ad interiora deserti*,^k in quo significatur⁷³ reduccio accionum omnium et affectionum ad inti-

⁶¹ hauritur] haurit q

⁶² quod hauritur... confortatur] quod haurit anima deuota in hoc Sacramento, est, quod confortatur q

⁶³ Quia propter hoc] Unde q

⁶⁴ proficere] *corr. interl. alia manu ex prospicere M*

⁶⁵ Ambulauit] Ambulat q

⁶⁶ numerus] *om. q*

⁶⁷ per... dies] quadraginta diebus q

⁶⁸ Secundo] *add. in marg. ut uid. 2^o M*

⁶⁹ et propter hoc] unde q

⁷⁰ perueniebat] pervenerat q

⁷¹ perueniebat Moyses] pervenerat Moyses q

⁷² unde] de quo legitur Exodi tertio q

⁷³ significatur] designatur q

ⁱ Ambulauit... diebus] III Reg. 19, 8.

^j pascebat oves] Ex. 3, 1.

^k minauit... deserti] Ex. 3, 1.

^{viii} denarius numerus] Cfr RABANUS MAURUS, *De universo* 18.3; PL 111:489B.

^{ix} Per denarium... decalogus] HIERONYMUS STRIDONENSIS, *In Hieremiam prophetam* 6.34.3; CSEL 59:419; cfr ANSELMUS LAUDUNENSIS, *Enarrationes in Matthaem* 18; PL 162:1409C.

ma cordis. Et peruenit *usque*⁷⁴ *ad montem Dei*, et in hoc⁷⁵ notatur sublevacio mentis ad celestia. Et ibi *apparuit ei Dominus*, quia extendatur⁷⁶ actus anime contemplantis. Apparuit autem ei in flamma ignis. Ignis habet calefacere et illuminare, ad significandum⁷⁷ quando <anima peruenit>⁷⁸ ad gratiam contemplacionis, et intellectus haurit lumen cognicionis et similiter⁷⁹ affectus incendium dileccionis.

33. Tercio,⁸ disponit⁸¹ ad diuinorum secretorum reuelacionem: et ideo dicitur hic, quod dixit Dominus⁸² Helie: *Egredere et sta in monte coram Domino*: et spiritus pertransiuit,⁸³ *et spiritus grandis et fortis subuertens montes et conterens petras ante Dominum: non in spiritu Dominus; <et post spiritum commocio: non in commocione Dominus: et post commocionem ignis, non in igne Dominus; et post ignem sybulus>*⁸⁴ *aure tenuis*,¹ et ibi Dominus. Ibi enim reuelatum est Helye,⁸⁵ quod Dominus non⁸⁶ in spiritu superbie, non in commocione impaciencie, non in igne cupiditatis siue carnalis concupiscencie, sed *in sybulo aure tenuis*, id est in tranquillitate pacate consciencie.⁸⁷ *In pace enim factus est locus eius.*^{m88}

34. Quarto,⁸⁹ animat⁹⁰ ad contemplacionem mundam,⁹¹ ideoque⁹² ad celestium bonorum desideracionem. Et hoc est quod dicitur,⁹³ Hel-

⁷⁴ usque] *om. q*

⁷⁵ et in hoc] in quo *q*

⁷⁶ extendatur... contemplantis] ex tunc datur anime actus contemplationis *q*

⁷⁷ significandum] *add. quod M*

⁷⁸ anima peruenit] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁷⁹ similiter] *om. q*

⁸⁰ Tercio] *add. in marg. 3° M*

⁸¹ disponit] *disponitur q*

⁸² dixit dominus] *Dominus dixerit q*

⁸³ et spiritus pertransiuit] et ecce, Dominis transit *q*

⁸⁴ et post spiritum commocio... post ignem sibilus] *add. ut Vulg. ex q : post sybulus M*

⁸⁵ Helye] *add. in marg. nota M*

⁸⁶ non] non est *q*

⁸⁷ consciencie] *add. Psalmus q*

⁸⁸ locus eius] *add. et habitacio eius in Sion ut Vulg. q*

⁸⁹ Quarto] *add. in marg. 4° M*

⁹⁰ animat] *animatur q*

⁹¹ contemplacionem mundam] *contemptum mundi q*

⁹² ideoque] et *q*

⁹³ dicitur] *add. hic, quod q*

¹ Egredere... tenuis] III Reg. 19, 11-12

^m In pace... Sion] Ps. 75, 3.

yas operuit⁹⁴ uultum suum pallio, et egressus stetit in ostio speluncae. Quando enim anima subleuatur ad uidendam illius pulchritudinis immensitatem <et uirtutis>⁹⁵ deitatis⁹⁶ diuine infinitatem, statim resilit in propriam paruitatem et cooperuit⁹⁷ uultum suum per profundam humilitatem, et egreditur <de>⁹⁸ mundi cupiditate,⁹⁹ et stat in ostio speluncae, id est, suspirat ad eternitatem. Per speluncam enim significatur corpus humanum, per ostium exeundi desiderium. Et propter hoc stat¹⁰⁰ quasi in ostio, quia exire desiderabat.

35. Confiteantur ergo *Domino nomine eius*, et cetera,¹⁰¹ quia¹⁰² praefigurauit nobis corpus suum sub¹⁰³ figura panis.

<III.> De figura mellis¹

36. Tercio praefigurauit nobis corpus suum reuerentissimum sub² figura mellis. Unde³ Proverbiorum uigesimo quarto: *Comede, fili mi,*⁴ *mel, quia bonum est et fauus dulcis gutturi tuo.*^{5a} Per fauum mellis significatur sacramentum dominici corporis; et bene per mel [f. 50v] significatur, quia mel delectat gustum, et secundum medicos purificare habet uisum.ⁱ Ita Christus delectat affectum, et illuminat intellectum. Unde⁶

⁹⁴ operuit] aperuit ut uid. M

⁹⁵ et uirtutis] add. ex q : om. M

⁹⁶ deitatis] om. q

⁹⁷ cooperuit] cooperit q

⁹⁸ de] add. ex q : om. M

⁹⁹ de mundi cupiditate] mundi cupiditatem M

¹⁰⁰ stat] stabat post ostio q

¹⁰¹ nomine eius, et cetera] om. q

¹⁰² quia] add. secundo q

¹⁰³ sub] sanctissimum in q

¹ De figura mellis] rub. M

² sub] in q

³ unde] Et propter hoc dicitur q

⁴ mi] om. q

⁵ tuo] meo q

⁶ Unde] om. q

^a Comede... tuo] Prov. 24, 13.

ⁱ purificare uisum] cfr. A. CORNELIUS CELSUS, *De medicina libri viii* 6.6; ed. Daremberg, 236; et PLINIUS MAIOR, *Naturalis historia* 11.38; ed. Mayhoff, 2:295.

Bernardus: 'Iesus, dulcedo cordium, fons uiuus, lumen mencium, excedit omne gaudium et omne desiderium'.ⁱⁱ Per hoc enim quomodo⁷ dicit, quod est dulcedo cordium, delectare habet affectum,⁸ per hoc autem quod dicit⁹ lumen mencium illuminare habet intellectum.

37. Quod autem Christus sit mel, dicit Bernardus super Cantica:¹⁰ 'Iesus mel¹¹ in ore, melos in aure, iubilus in corde'.ⁱⁱⁱ Et alibi: 'Iesus, decus angelicum, <in>¹² aure dulce canticum, in ore mel mirificum, in corde pigmentum celicum'.^{iv} Hoc mel produxit¹³ apis nostra, scilicet¹⁴ Virgo Maria, iuxta illud [p. 559] Ecclesiastici:¹⁵ *Breuis in uolatilibus apis et inicum dulcoris habet fructus eius*.^b Apis <est>¹⁶ beata Virgo, que breuis dicitur inter uolatilia,¹⁷ quia inter omnes sanctos humillima. Huius fructus habet inicum dulcoris, quia Dominus Iesus,¹⁸ qui fuit fructus uentris eius, non solum fuit dulcis sicut mel ymo *super mel et fauum*.^c Unde Bernardus: 'Super mel et omnia dulcis Iesu presencia'.^v Sicut ergo prefiguratur corpus Christi sub figura panis, et hoc ad refeccionem esuriencium, ita prefiguratum in¹⁹ figura mellis ad illuminationem in umbra mortis iacencium,²⁰ et hoc est quod dicitur

⁷ quomodo] quod *q*

⁸ affectum] *praem. et exp. intellectum M*

⁹ dicit] est *q*

¹⁰ Cantica] Canticum *q*

¹¹ mel] *add. est q*

¹² in] *add. ex q : om. M*

¹³ produxit] *add. nobis q*

¹⁴ scilicet] *om. q*

¹⁵ Ecclesiastici] *add. undecimo q*

¹⁶ est] *add. ex q : om. M*

¹⁷ inter uolatilia] *om. q*

¹⁸ Iesus] *add. Christus q*

¹⁹ in] est sub *q*

²⁰ iacencium] *sedentium q*

^b Breuis... eius] Eccli. 11, 3.

^c super... fauum] Eccli. 24, 27.

ⁱⁱ Iesus... desiderium] cfr AUCTORIS INCERTI Iubilus rhythmicus *Iesu dulcis memoria*; PL 184:1317.

ⁱⁱⁱ Iesus... corde] BERNARDUS CLARAEVALLENSIS, Sermones super Cantica Canticorum 15.6; ed. Leclercq, 1: 86; PL 183: 847A.

^{iv} Iesus... celicum] cfr *Iesu dulcis memoria*, ut supra.

^v Super... presencia] cfr *Iesu dulcis memoria*, ut supra.

primo Regum,²¹ Ionathas gustauit de melle, quando²² *illuminati sunt oculi eius*.^d

38. Sed hec²³ quatuor sunt homini necessaria accedenti digne ad hoc sacramentum. Ideo legitur Ionathas quatuor fecisse priusquam uenisset ad²⁴ favum mellis: ascendit enim ad²⁵ laboriosam uiam, conuertit totum exercitum Phylistinorum in fugam, tenens²⁶ in manu sua uirgam suam,²⁷ et ad os²⁸ applicuit manum suam, ad significandum quod digne accedens <ad hoc sacramentum>²⁹ debet habere conatum melioracionis, uictoriam temptacionis, patrociniū beate Virginis, et presidium illuminate operacionis.

39. Primo ergo debet habere conatum melioracionis: et propter hoc legitur etiam de Ionatha, quod *ascendit Ionathas*³⁰ *reptans manibus et pedibus*,^e ad significandum quod desiderium magnum debet semper habere proficiendi, crescendi et ascendendi de uirtute in uirtutem, iuxta illud <Psalmi>:³¹ *Beatus uir, cuius est auxilium abs te, ascensiones in corde suo disposuit* [f. 51r] *<in ualle lacrymarum, in loco, quem posuit. Etenim benedictionem dabit legislator: ibunt de uirtute in uirtute>*,³² *uidebitur Deus deorum in Syon*,^f et quia nullus ad hoc ydoneus est, nisi applicet sibi³³ ad hoc omnes uires anime et corporis, ideo dicitur Ionathas *reptasse manibus et pedibus*. Bernardus:³⁴ *Hec est cotidiana exercitatio mea: assidue scopo spiritum meum, et cum omnibus amabilibus meis*³⁵ quasi pedibus et manibus et totis uiribus innitens ascendo superius, et quanto magis tendo superius, tanto detrudor

²¹ Regum] *add.* decimo quarto quod *q*

²² quando] et *q*

²³ hec] quia *q*

²⁴ ad] *add.* gustandum *q*

²⁵ enim ad] *om.* *q*

²⁶ tenens] tenuit *q*

²⁷ suam] *om.* *q*

²⁸ os] *add.* suum *q*

²⁹ ad hoc sacramentum] *add.* *ex q* : *om.* *M*

³⁰ Ionathas] *om.* *q*

³¹ Psalmi] *add.* *ex q* : *om.* *M*

³² in ualle... uirtutem] *add.* *ut Vulg.* *ex q* : usquequo *M*

³³ applicet sibi] qui applicet *q*

³⁴ Bernardus] *add in marg.* nota bernardus *M*

³⁵ meis] tuis *expunc.* et *corr.* in *marg.* *M*

^d Ionathas... oculi eius] cfr I Reg. 14, 29

^e ascendit... pedibus] I Reg. 14, 13

^f Beatus... Sion] Ps. 83, 6-8

durius in memetipsum, et respiciens me factus sum mihi de memetipsum laboriosa questio'.^{36vi}

40. Secundo debet habere uictoriam temptacionis: et propter hoc legitur <de Ionatha>,³⁷ quod conuertit totum exercitum Phylistinorum³⁸ in fugam, ad significandum quod in omnibus temptacionibus suis³⁹ debet peruenire ad uictoriam qui <uult>⁴⁰ degustare dulcedinem huius mellis in sacramento altaris absconditum.⁴¹

41. Tercio debet habere patrociniū beate⁴² Virginis, qui cupit digne accedere ad sacramentum altaris.⁴³ Et propter hoc legitur Ionathas in manibus suis⁴⁴ tenuisse uirgam, priusquam uenisset⁴⁵ ad dulcedinem melleam. Per uirgam significatur Virgo Maria, iuxta⁴⁶ illud Ysaie:⁴⁷ *Egredietur uirga de radice Yesse*.^{48g} Ille ergo in manibus tenet uirgam, qui in omni operatione sua habet beate Virginis memoriam, cuius <extensione>⁴⁹ mel attingitur, quia non nisi patrociniis⁵⁰ beate⁵¹ Virginis ad uirtutem huius sacramenti peruenitur;⁵² sicut per eam istud sacratissimum corpus nobis est datum, ita per manus eius debet offerri, et per manus eius debet⁵³ accipi sub sacramento, quod nobis presti-

³⁶ ascendo... questio] sursum tendo ad te; sed quanto tendo fortius, tanto detrudor durius in terram, in memetipsum et sub memetipsum, et respiciens memetipsum, factus sum mihi ipsi de memetipso laboriosa et taediosa quaestio q

³⁷ de Ionatha] *add. ex q : om. M*

³⁸ Phylistinorum] *om. q*

³⁹ suis] *om. q*

⁴⁰ uult] *corr. ex q : deberet M*

⁴¹ degustare... absconditum] digne accedere ad Sacramentum altaris q

⁴² beate] *add. Mariae q*

⁴³ cupit... altaris] vult gustare huius mellis dulcedinem in Sacramento altaris absconditum q

⁴⁴ manibus suis] manu sua q

⁴⁵ uenisset] ueniret q

⁴⁶ Maria iuxta] *add. in scriptura secundum q*

⁴⁷ Ysaie] *add. undecimo q*

⁴⁸ Yesse] *add. et flos de radice eius ascendet ut Vulg. q*

⁴⁹ extensione] *corr. ex q : ascensionis M*

⁵⁰ patrociniis] patricinio q

⁵¹ beate] *add. Mariae q*

⁵² peruenitur] *add. Et propter hoc q*

⁵³ debet] *om. q*

^g Egredietur... Iesse] Is. 11, 1

^{vi} Hec est... questio] cfr GUILLELMUS ABBAS, De contemplar Deo 2.5; PL 184:369C.

tum est et natum ex eius utero. Bernardus: 'Quidquid est illud, quod offerre paras,⁵⁴ Marie manibus recommendare memento, ut in⁵⁵ eodem aluo gracia ad largitorem graciae refluat, quo influxit. Forte enim manus tue aut sanguine plene sunt,⁵⁶ aut infecte muneribus, eo quod eas ab omni opere⁵⁷ non excussisti'.^{vii}

42. Quarto debet habere presidium illuminate operacionis qui digne uult accedere ad [p. 560] corpus⁵⁸ Christi, sicut dicit Apostolus:⁵⁹ *Qui non laborat, non manducet.*^h Hoc perfectissime debet seruari circa manducacionem corporis Christi. Nullus enim ad huius sacramenti manducacionem⁶¹ est idoneus, nisi qui exercitatus est per [f. 51v] bonam operacionem. Et propter hoc dicitur quod Ionathas,⁶² *applicauit manum suam ad os,*ⁱ quia manibus operamus,⁶³ et ideo in scripturis per manus operacio significatur; ore uero quia manducamus, <ideo hoc nomine oris>⁶⁴ significatur actus manducacionis. *Manum ergo ad os applicauit*⁶⁵ qui ipsi manducacioni corporis Christi exhibet⁶⁶ exercitium bone operacionis.

43. Sed quia digne manducanti augmentari solet donum graciae, ideo quatuor bona legitur Ionathas accepisse in degustacione mellis, ad significandum quod quatuor effectus graciae in sacramento accipit, qui digne accedit. Ibi enim illuminatur oculi rationabiles⁶⁷ ad cogno-

⁵⁴ paras] *add.* beatae *q*

⁵⁵ in] *om.* *q*

⁵⁶ sunt] *om.* *q*

⁵⁷ opere] munere *q*

⁵⁸ corpus] mysterium corporis *q*

⁵⁹ Apostolus] *add.* ad Thessalonicenses *q*

⁶⁰ non... laborat] non uult operari, sive qui non laborat *q*

⁶¹ manducacionem] perceptionem *q*

⁶² quod Ionathas] de Ionatha quod *q*

⁶³ operamus et] laboramus *q*

⁶⁴ ideo... oris] *add.* *ex q : om. M*

⁶⁵ applicauit] applicat *q*

⁶⁶ exhibet] adhibet *q*

⁶⁷ oculi rationabiles] rationalis *q*

^h Qui... manducet] cfr 2 Thess. 3, 10

ⁱ applicuit... os] cfr I Reg. 14, 26

^{vii} Quidquid... excussisti] BERNARDUS CLARAEVALLENSIS, Sermo in Natiuitate Beatae Virginis Mariae 18; ed. Leclercq, 5: 28; PL 183:448A.

scendum summe⁶⁸ uerum; et ideo legitur, postquam⁶⁹ gustauit de melle,⁷⁰ *illuminati sunt oculi eius*.^j Qui enim frequentat hoc sacramentum cum feruore deuocionis de die in diem proficit in illuminatione mentis. Et propter hoc dicitur, *Vidistis*,⁷¹ *quia illuminati sunt oculi mei*, eo quod gustauerim *paululum de melle*.^{72k}

44. Secundo, ibi irritatur⁷³ concupiscibilitas⁷⁴ ad querendum summe⁷⁵ bonum. Qui enim digne accedit ad hoc sacramentum magis ac magis afficitur et in intimis suis delectatur. Et hoc est quod hic dicitur de Ionatha: *Gustans gustauit paululum de melle*.^{76l} Notabile est quod dicit: *Gustans gustauit*: cum enim illa dulcedo gustatur, concupiscibilitas⁷⁷ magis <ad gustandum irritatur,⁷⁸ et quasi ad> magis capiendum dilatatur.⁷⁹ Ideo, qui⁸⁰ gustando gustat, ex gustu⁸¹ semper desiderium ampliat. Unde Bernardus: ‘Gustus spiritualis incitamentum est amoris et irritamentum desiderii’.^{viii} Idem alibi:⁸² ‘Qui te gustant esuriunt, qui bibunt adhuc siciunt, desiderare nesciunt nisi Iesum, quem sensunt’.^{83ix} Et bene subiungit *paululum mellis*, quia, quantumcumque homini in

⁶⁸ summe] summum *q*

⁶⁹ postquam] *add.* Ionathas *q*

⁷⁰ de melle] mel *q*

⁷¹ Vidistis] *add.* ipsi *ut Vulg.* *q*

⁷² melle] *add.* isto *q*

⁷³ irritatur] incitatur *q*

⁷⁴ concupiscibilitas] concupiscibilis *q*

⁷⁵ summe] summum *q*

⁷⁶ de melle] mellis *ut Vulg.* *q*

⁷⁷ concupiscibilitas] concupiscibilis *q*

⁷⁸ magis... quasi ad] *om. per hom. M*

⁷⁹ et quasi... dilatatur] magis ad gustandum irritatur et magis dilatatur *q*

⁸⁰ qui] quia *q*

⁸¹ gustu] gusta *q*

⁸² alibi] *om. q*

⁸³ sensunt] diligunt *q*

^j illuminati... eius] I Reg. 14, 27

^k paululum... melle] cfr I Reg. 14, 43

^l gustans... melle] cfr I Reg. 14, 43

^{viii} gustus... desiderii] cfr BERNARDUS CLARAEVALLENSIS, *Sermones in festiuitate Omnium Sanctorum*, serm.1.10; ed. Leclercq, 5:336; PL 183:458D.

^{ix} qui te... diligunt] *Iesu dulcis memoria, ut supra*, PL 184:1317.

uita detur⁸⁴ ampla degustacio, tamen in comparacione illius plenitudinis⁸⁵ non est nisi quasi⁸⁶ *paululum mellis*.

45. Tercio, fortificatur irascibilitas⁸⁷ ad extirpandum omne malum. Et propter hoc legitur hic, quod Ionathas, confortatus de melle,⁸⁸ persecutus est Phylisteos usque Hailon. Phylistei interpretantur 'duplex ruina',^x et significant uicia, que ruere faciunt corpus et [f. 51v] animam morte eterna. Hailon interpretatur 'inquisicio uite',^{xi} et significat eternam uitam, quia⁸⁹ ibi perfecte⁹⁰ acquirimus uitam.⁹¹ Hec enim temporalis uita 'non est dicenda uita, sed potius mors'.^{92 xii} Ionathas,⁹³ confortatus de melle, id est uir sanctus roboratus Dei corpore,⁹⁴ persequitur Phylisteos usque Hailon, id est uicia exterminare non cessat, donec uitam eternam possideat.

46. Quarto, totus homo⁹⁵ mortificatur ad uiuendum secundum Deum. Unde postquam Ionathas dixisset,⁹⁶ *Gustans gustauit de melle*;⁹⁷ consequenter subiunxit: *Et ecce*⁹⁸ *morior*,^m ad significandum quod quemcumque dulcedo huius sacramenti perfuderit,⁹⁹ huic mundo funditus extinguitur.¹⁰⁰ Et hoc est desiderium sanctorum, unde Iob:

⁸⁴ in uita detur degustacio ampla] detur in hac uita ampla degustatio q

⁸⁵ plenitudinis] *add.* supernae q

⁸⁶ quasi] *om.* q

⁸⁷ irascibilitas] irascibilis q

⁸⁸ de melle] gustu mellis q

⁸⁹ quia] quam q

⁹⁰ perfecte] perfectissime q

⁹¹ acquirimus uitam] acquiramus q

⁹² mors] *add.* sicut dicit Gregorius q

⁹³ Ionathas] *add.* ergo q

⁹⁴ uir... corpore] uir factus de corpore Christi q

⁹⁵ totius homo] homo mundo q

⁹⁶ Unde... dixisset] Et hoc est quod dicitur hic de Ionatha. Postquam dixit q

⁹⁷ gustauit] *om.*, *et add.* uidelicet paululum de melle q

⁹⁸ et ecce] ecce, ego q

⁹⁹ perfuderit] perfundit q

¹⁰⁰ extinguitur] extinguit q

^m et... morior] I Reg. 14, 43

^x duplex ruina] HIERONYMUS STRIDONENSIS, *Liber interpretationis hebraicorum nominum* s.v. Filistiim; ed. de Lagarde, CCSL 72:66; PL 23:779B.

^{xi} inquisicio uite] *Fontem non inueni*

^{xii} potius mors] cfr AUGUSTINUS HIPPONENSIS, *De ciuitate Dei* 12.21; ed. Hoffman, CSEL 40.1:601; PL 41:369

*Suspendium elegit anima mea, et mortem ossa mea:*ⁿ huiusmodi enim hominis exterioris mortificacio est interioris summa uiuificacio. Unde dixit Dominus Moysi: *Non uidebit me homo et uiuet,*^o <quia non nisi>¹⁰¹ post istam mortificacionem uenitur¹⁰² ad Dei uisionem. Quia¹⁰³ ergo 'uisio Dei est tota nostra¹⁰⁴ merces', sicut docet¹⁰⁵ Augustinus,^{xiii} et non uenitur¹⁰⁶ ad uisionem Dei¹⁰⁷ nisi per mortificacionem. Ideo¹⁰⁸ Augustinus hanc mortificacionem desiderabat¹⁰⁹ dicens: 'Fac me, Domine, tuo desiderio et tuo amore huic mundo funditus exstingui, et omnium transeuncium rerum uanitatem obliuisci,¹¹⁰ ut pre magnitudine amoris tui nec¹¹¹ de temporalibus lugeam, nec gaudeam, nec blandimentis¹¹² corrumpar nec aduersis concutiar.'^{xiv}

47. *Confiteantur ergo Domino misericordie eius, et cetera, <quia prefigurauit nobis corpus suum sub figura mellis>.*¹¹³ [p. 561]

<IV.> *De figura agni*¹

48. Quarto prefigurauit nobis corpus suum sub figura agni paschalis. Unde Exodi duodecimo: *Tollat unusquisque agnum per domos et fami-*

¹⁰¹ quia non nisi] *corr. ex q : nisi enim M*

¹⁰² uenitur] *pervenitur q*

¹⁰³ quia] *om. q*

¹⁰⁴ tota] *om. nostra q*

¹⁰⁵ docet] *dixit q*

¹⁰⁶ uenitur] *pervenitur q*

¹⁰⁷ uisionem Dei] *Dei uisionem q*

¹⁰⁸ ideo] *add. beatus q*

¹⁰⁹ hanc mortificacionem desiderabat] *desiderabat hanc mortificacionem q*

¹¹⁰ obliuisci] *om. q*

¹¹¹ nec] *ut q*

¹¹² blandimentis] *blandis q*

¹¹³ quia... mellis] *add. ex q : om. M*

¹ De figura agni] *rub. M*

ⁿ suspendium... mea] *Iob 7, 15*

^o non... uiuet] *Ex. 33, 20*

^{xiii} uisio... merces] *AUGUSTINUS HIPPONENSIS, Enarrationes in Psalmos 90.2.13; ed. Dekkers, CCSL 39:1177; PL 37:1170.*

^{xiv} Fac me... concutiar] *ANSELMUS CANTUARIENSIS, Oratio 17; PL 158:896A; cfr PSEUDO-AUGUSTINUS HIPPONENSIS, Meditationes 35; PL 40:929.*

*lias*² *suas*.^a Est autem agnus *sine*³ *macula*.^{4b} Iste agnus preuisus fuit⁵ per prophetam Ysaie duodecimo:⁶ *Emitte agnum, Domine, dominatorem terre de petra deserti*.^{7c} Iste agnus fuit sine macula, qui⁸ uenerat tollere peccata mundi; unde Iohannis primo: *Ecce, agnus Dei*,⁹ *qui tollit peccata mundi*.^d

49. Et quia agnus iste significat sanctissimum¹⁰ corpus Christi, ideo determinatur nobis qualiter¹¹ [f. 52v] debeat esse homo, antequam accedat, et qualis in ipso accessu, et quid¹² fructus recipiat post ipsam assumptionem.¹³ Antequam¹⁴ accedat, debet homo habere quatuor. Debet enim habere respectum ad uniuersitatem, debet se disponere ad ydoneitatem, debet accendi ad caritatem, et debet uenire ad integritatem.¹⁵

50. Primo ergo debet accedens habere respectum ad uniuersitatem, non enim sacerdos in persona sui solius, sed in persona uniuersitatis debet offerre. Et hoc est quod hic dicitur: *Immolabit eum uniuersa multitudo filiorum Israel*.^e Per manus enim omnium uiuentium debet offerre pro redemptione in purgatorio existencium, et per manus uiuorum et mortuorum ad laudem et gloriam omnium electorum,¹⁶ angelorum et hominum, in uita eterna regnancium, et per manus uniuersitatis ad honorem et gloriam¹⁷ sancte Trinitatis.

51. Secundo debet se preparare ad ydoneitatem. Et hoc est quod subiungitur: *Et sument de sanguine eius, ac ponent super utrumque*

² domos et familias] familias et domos *q*

³ Est autem agnus sine] Agnus autem erit absque *q*

⁴ sine macula] Ex. 12, 5

⁵ fuit] fuerat *q*

⁶ per prophetam Ysaie duoecimo] unde Isaias *q*

⁷ de petra deserti] *om. q*

⁸ qui] quia *q*

⁹ Dei] *add. et ecce q*

¹⁰ et quia... sanctissimum] agnus iste paschalis significat corpus Christi *q*

¹¹ qualiter] hic, qualis *q*

¹² quid] quot *q*

¹³ assumptionem] accessum *q*

¹⁴ Antequam] Ante enim quam *q*

¹⁵ ad integritatem] ad fidei integritatem *q*

¹⁶ electorum] sanctorum *q*

¹⁷ et gloriam] *om. q*

^a Tollat... suas] Ex. 12, 3

^b sine macula] Leu. 9, 3; Deut. 12, 15

^c emitte... deserti] Is. 16, 1

^d ecce... mundi] Io. 1, 29

^e Immolabit... Israel] Ex. 12, 6

*postem, et in superliminaribus domorum <in quibus>*¹⁸ *comedent illum.*^f Per duos postes et superliminare, que faciunt ostium,¹⁹ significantur tria in anima, per que Deus in eam²⁰ ingreditur ad habitaculum cordis, uidelicet rationalis, per quam ingreditur Deus ut lumen uel²¹ claritas; concupiscibilitas,²² per quam ingreditur Deus ut dulcedo et bonitas; irascibilitas,²³ per quam ingreditur Deus²⁴ ut gloria et immensitas. Hec tria tinguntur in sanguine, quando circa passionem Christi occupantur. Rationalitas sanguine agni tingitur, quando huius²⁵ sacramenti rimatur uirtutem.²⁶ Concupiscibilitas²⁷ tingitur, quando cognita ueritate, patienti Christo²⁸ compaciens amaricatur.²⁹ Irascibilitas³⁰ tunc tingitur, quando cognito Christo passo ad imitationem animatur.

52. Tercio debet accendi³¹ ad caritatem, et hoc est quod additur: *Et edent carnes nocte illa assas igni.*^g Per ignem istum significatur caritas, quam iussit Dominus in ara cordis nostri³² semper ardere.ⁱ In hoc igne debent³³ carnes corporis Christi assari, quia non nisi in caritate debet³⁴ manducari. Ille crudas carnes comedit, qui ad sacramentum sine caritate accedit. Sed qui crudas carnes [f. 53r] comedit, uitam suam³⁵ in

¹⁸ in quibus] *add. ut Vulg. q : om. M*

¹⁹ ostium] *add. in domum q*

²⁰ in eam] *om. q*

²¹ lumen uel] *lux sive q*

²² concupiscibilitas] *conuscibilis q*

²³ irascibilitas] *irascibilis q*

²⁴ Deus] *om. q*

²⁵ huius] *om. q*

²⁶ rimatur uirtutem] *veritatem miratur q*

²⁷ Concupiscibilitas] *concupiscibilis q*

²⁸ patienti Christo] *Christo passo q*

²⁹ amaricatur] *amaritur ut uid. M*

³⁰ Irascibilitas] *irascibilis q*

³¹ accendi] *corr. ex attendi in marg. M*

³² nostri] *om. q*

³³ debent] *dicuntur q*

³⁴ debet] *debent q*

³⁵ suam] *om. q*

^f et sument... illum] Ex. 12, 7

^g Et edent... igni] Ex. 12, 8

ⁱ Per ignem... ardere] cfr RABANUS MAURUS, *Commentaria in libros IV Regum* 3.9; PL 109:192A

periculo ponit, ita manducans corpus Christi et non habens dilectionem meretur eternam dampnationem.

53. Quarto debet habere fidei integritatem, et hoc est quod iungitur,³⁶ *Caput cum pedibus eius et intestinis uorabitis*.^h Per caput signatur³⁷ deitas:³⁸ *<Caput enim Christi est Deus>*;³⁹ⁱ sicut dicit Apostolus, et per⁴⁰ pedes, humanitas. Deus enim ubique est et non potest moueri de loco ad⁴¹ locum: quasi ergo pedes diuinitas⁴² assumpsit, quando in assumpto homine de loco ad locum ambulauit. Hos pedes^j dum Thob-yas, id est Christus, lauit in flumine, id est, exposuit in cruce: piscem eosdem⁴³ absorbere uolentem, id est dyabolum, manifestando eius nequicias uicit. Intestina sunt circa hoc sacramentum inattingibilia; que omnia debet homo uorare, quia omnia fideliter debet credere, eciam que non potest intellectu attingere.ⁱⁱ Ibi eciam debet credere esse uerum corpus Christi, quod traxit de beata Virgine: est autem ibi per transsubstancionem: anima uero est ibi per naturalem colligacionem; diuinitas est ibi per insuperabilem⁴⁴ unionem. Sunt eciam ibi utriusque nature intestina, id est sacramenta inexplicabilia. Et ideo qui non potest alicuius⁴⁵ huius sacramenti⁴⁶ intellectu capere, debet hoc Spiritus sancti potestati committere. Et hoc est quod dicitur: *Si quid residuum fuerit, igne comburentis*.^k

³⁶ iungitur] adiungitur *q*

³⁷ signatur] significatur *q*

³⁸ deitas] Diuinitas *q*

³⁹ Caput... Deus] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁴⁰ et per] *om. q*

⁴¹ ad] *in q*

⁴² diuinitas] *om. q*

⁴³ eosdem] *eos post absorbere q*

⁴⁴ insuperabilem] inseparabilem *q*

⁴⁵ alicuius] *om. q*

⁴⁶ sacramenti] *add. altitudinem q*

^h caput... uorabitis] Ex. 12, 9

ⁱ caput... Deus] I Cor. 11, 3

^j Hos pedes] cfr Tob. 6, 2

^k si... comburentis] Ex. 12, 10

ⁱⁱ Hos pedes... attingere] cfr *Glossa ordinaria* in Tob. 6, 2; *Bibliorum sacrorum cum glossa ordinaria...*, tom. 2, Venice: [s.n.], 1603, cols 1523–1524.

54. Debet eciam homo habere quatuor⁴⁷ in ipso accessu, uidelicet⁴⁸ in carne continenciam, in affectu mundiciam, in animo passionis Christi memoriam, in desiderio uitam eternam.

55. Primo ergo debet habere in carne continenciam, unde dicitur hic,[p. 561] *Renes vestros accingetis*.¹ In renibus est sedes luxurie, et ideo renes accingit qui per continenciam fluxum libidinis restringit.

56. <Secundo>⁴⁹ debet eciam⁵⁰ in affectibus habere⁵¹ mundiciam, et hoc est quod additur: *Calciamenta habebitis in pedibus*.^m Pedes⁵² enim in Scriptura affectus significant,⁵³ⁱⁱⁱ quia sicut mouetur pedibus ipsum corpus,⁵⁴ sic anima mouetur suis affectibus; et hii pedes debent calciari, id est, ab omni terrenitate abstrahi. Sed quia nihil ita tenet affectus nostros mundos sicut meditacio Scripturarum, ideo hortatur nos Apostolus, ut simus *calciati in preparacione euangelii pacis*.ⁿ

57. Tercio debet accedens habere in animo suo passionis Christi memoriam, unde⁵⁵ dicitur hic, *Tenentes in manibus baculos*.^o Per baculum autem significatur crux Christi.⁵⁶ *In isto baculo* Iacob, id est Christus, *transiuit Iordanem*, id est mundi defluxum,⁵⁷ et reduxit secum *duas turmas*,^p id est multas animas ex [f. 53v] gentibus et Iudeis aggregatas.⁵⁸ Baculum ergo in manibus tenet qui passionem Christi in

⁴⁷ habere quatuor] quatuor habere *q*

⁴⁸ uidelicet] *add. primo q*

⁴⁹ Secundo] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁵⁰ Debet eciam] Secundo debet *q*

⁵¹ in affectibus habere] habere in affectu *q*

⁵² Pedes] Per pedes *q*

⁵³ significant] significantur *q*

⁵⁴ mouetur pedibus ipsum corpus] corpus mouetur pedibus *q*

⁵⁵ debet... Unde] *om. q*

⁵⁶ Christi] *om. q*

⁵⁷ mundi defluxum] fluxum mundi *q*

⁵⁸ aggregatas] congregatas *q*

¹ renes... accingetis] Ex. 12, 11

^m calciamenta... pedibus] Ex. 12, 11

ⁿ calceati... pacis] Eph. 6, 15

^o Tenentes... baculos] Ex. 12, 11

^p In isto baculo... turmas] cfr Gen. 32, 7-10

ⁱⁱⁱ Cfr ALEXANDER HALENSIS, *Glossa in quattuor libros Sententiarum: glossa in librum quartum*, dist. 24 (De ordinibus), n. 13a; ed. PP. Collegii S. Bonaventurae, 432.

memoriam habet;⁵⁹ et hoc iussit Dominus, cum sacramentum hoc instituit dicens: *Hoc facite, quocienscumque sumitis, in meam commemorationem.*^q

58. Quarto debet habere in desiderio uitam eternam; et hoc est quod subiungitur: *Et <comedetis> festinantes.*^{60r} Hoc significat⁶¹ quod qui manducat hoc sacramentum debet festinare ad plenitudinis eius cumulum. Per huius enim dulcedinis gustum prouocatur ad gaudium plenum; et hoc est quod additur: *Est enim phase, id est transitus, Domini.*^s Unde iste agnus⁶² in figura datus fuit⁶³ filiis Israel in exitu de Egypto. Hoc significat,⁶⁴ quod qui deuote accipit hoc sacramentum, transit de hoc mundo ad Deum.

59. Quinto,⁶⁵ quatuor fructus percipit qui digne accedit ad hoc sacramentum. Et propter hoc post esum agni huius quatuor Dominus facit: per terram Egypti transit,⁶⁶ primogenita percutit, in diis Egypti iudicia⁶⁷ facit, et insignitos sanguine a plaga custodit, ad significandum quod digne communicantibus consolacionem immittit, fomitem immittit, amorem mundi tollit, et in die iudicii securos facit.⁶⁸

60. Primo ergo consolacionem immittit; et hoc est quod dicitur: *Et transibo per terram Egypti.*^t Egyptus 'tenebre' interpretatur,^{iv} et significat cor humanum nondum perfecte illuminatum. Hoc Dominus per-

⁵⁹ passionem Christi in memoriam habet] memoriam passionis Christi in animo tenet *q*

⁶⁰ comedetis festinantes] *corr. ex* comedentes festinantes *M*: comedetis festinanter *ut Vulg. q*

⁶¹ hoc significat] ad significandum *q*

⁶² agnus] datus est *q*

⁶³ datus fuit] *om. q*

⁶⁴ Hoc significat] ad significandum *q*

⁶⁵ Quinto] Tertio notandum quod *q*

⁶⁶ per... transit] terram Aegypti pertransit *q*

⁶⁷ iudicia] iudicium *q*

⁶⁸ facit] reddit *q*

^q Hoc... commemoracionem] Luc 22, 19; I Cor. 11, 25

^r comedentes festinantes] cfr Ex. 12, 11

^s Est... Domini] Ex. 12, 11

^t Et transibo... Egypti] Ex. 12, 12.

^{iv} tenebre interpretatur] HIERONYMUS STRIDONENSIS, *Liber interpretationis hebraicorum nominum*, s.v. Aegyptus; ed. de Lagarde, CCSL 72:66; PL 23:890.

transit, quando consolacionem immittit: et bene *pertransit*, quia *ibi*⁶⁹ mansionem non facit, quia ipsum habile ad hoc non inuenit.⁷⁰ Tamen tamdiu *pertransire* potest,⁷¹ quod *ibidem* poterit sibi habitaculum facere, iuxta illud quod dicitur in persona fidelis anime⁷² quarto Regum:⁷³ *Animaduerto, quod uir Dei iste sanctus est, qui transit per nos frequenter. Faciamus ergo ei cenaculum paruum*, id est, preparemus ei cordis habitaculum: *et ponamus <ei in eo>*⁷⁴ *candelabrum* proprie recognicionis,⁷⁵ *mensam* interne refeccionis, *cellam*⁷⁶ quiete mentis,⁷⁷ *lectulum* contemplacionis, *ut, cum uenerit*,⁷⁸ *maneant ibi*.^u

61. Secundo fomitem minuit, et hoc est quod additur:⁷⁹ *Percuciam omne primogenitum in terra Egypti*.^v Quid <sunt>⁸⁰ primogenita nisi carnis uicia,⁸¹ que sunt nobis ingenita a primis <parentibus>?⁸² Et hec Dominus percutit, quando fomitem carnis imminuit: imminuit, dico,⁸³ non omnino tollit, quia sicut dicit Bernardus, 'Quantumcumque in hac uita profeceris, erras, si carnem tuam credis emortuam.⁸⁴ Velis, nolis, Ihebuseus [f. 54r] habitat intra terminos tuos;^w subiugari potest, exterminari non potest.'^v

⁶⁹ *ibi*] *add. sup. l. M*

⁷⁰ non inuenit] inuenit *q*

⁷¹ Tamen tamdiu *pertransire* potest] Tamdiu tamen potest *pertransire q*

⁷² fidelis anime] fidelium *q*

⁷³ quarto Regum] quarti Regum quarto *q*

⁷⁴ *ei in eo*] *corr. ex q : in ea M*

⁷⁵ recognicionis] cognitionis *q*

⁷⁶ *cellam*] *sellam ut Vulg. q*

⁷⁷ mentis] mansionis et *q*

⁷⁸ *uenerit*] *add. ad nos q*

⁷⁹ *et... additur*] ideo *additur q*

⁸⁰ *sunt*] *corr. ex q : est M*

⁸¹ *uicia*] *uilia q*

⁸² *parentibus*] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁸³ *imminuit dico*] *dico q*

⁸⁴ *emortuam*] *add. non magis oppressam q*

^u *Animaduerto... maneant ibi*] cfr IV Reg. 4, 9-10

^v *Percuciam... Egypti*] Ex. 12, 12

^w *Ihebuseus*] cfr Josh. 15, 63

^v *Quantumcumque... potest*] BERNARDUS CLARAEVALLENSIS, *Sermones super Cantica canticorum* 58.10; ed. Leclercq, 2:133; PL 183:1060D.

62. Tercio amorem mundi tollit, et hoc est quod hic dicitur: *Et in cunctis diis Egypti faciam iudicia.*^x Quid enim <dii>⁸⁵ Egypti nisi amabilia mundi significat?⁸⁶ 'Quod quisque pre ceteris diligit, hoc illi Deus est', sicut dicit Ambrosius.^{vi} Unde de carnalibus⁸⁷ ad Phylippenses: *Quorum Deus uenter est et gloria in confusione eorum.*^y In <his>⁸⁸ ergo Dominus Deus⁸⁹ iudicia facit, quando contemptum huius mundi ingignit.⁹⁰

63. Quarto digne accedentes in die iudicii securos reddet,⁹¹ et hoc est quod adiungitur: *Erit uobis autem sanguis in signum in edibus, in quibus [p. 563] eritis: et uidebo sanguinem et pertransibo uos, nec erit in uobis plaga disperdens, cum percussero terram Egypti.*^z In quibuscumque enim in die iudicii uiderit sanguinem sue redemptionis, eos liberabit a plaga eterne percussio, quando scilicet *percutiet terram uirga oris sui et spiritu labiorum suorum interficiet impium.*^{aa}

64. *Confiteantur ergo <Domino>*⁹² *misericordie eius,*⁹³ quia prefigurauit nobis corpus suum sub⁹⁴ figura agni paschalis.

<V.> *De figura thesauri*¹

65. Quinto prefigurauit nobis corpus suum sub figura thesauri celestis. Et bene comparatur corpus Christi thesauro, quia² in thesauro

⁸⁵ dii] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁸⁶ Quid... significat] Dii Aegypti sunt amabilia mundi *q*

⁸⁷ carnalibus] *add. dicitur q*

⁸⁸ his] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁸⁹ dominus deus] *Deus q*

⁹⁰ contemptum... ingignit] contemptum mundi gignit *q*

⁹¹ reddet] *facit q*

⁹² Domino] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁹³ misericordie eius] Domino misericordior *q*

⁹⁴ sub] *in q*

¹ De figura thesauri] *rub. M : om. q*

² quia] *add. sicut q*

^x Et... iudicia] Ex. 12, 12

^y Quorum... eorum] Phil. 3, 19

^z Erit... Egypti] Ex. 12, 13

^{aa} percutiet... impium] Is. 11, 4

^{vi} Ambrosius] cfr PETRUS LOMBARDUS, *Commentaria in Psalmos* 80.8; PL 191:772D.

reponuntur queque³ desiderabilia rerum humanarum,⁴ sic et in <corpore>⁵ Christi reposita sunt omnia carismata graciaram: et hoc est, quod Pater,⁶ uolens⁷ sponsam filii sui,⁸ scilicet sanctam ecclesiam matrem <consolari>,⁹ ante aduentum¹⁰ promittebat¹¹ hos thesauros dicens: *Tibi dabo thesauros absconditos*.^{12a} Hii thesauri dicuntur bene *absconditi*, quia sunt in¹³ sacramento uisibili uelati. Et notabile est quod dicit: *Tibi dabo thesauros*, in plurali. Quatuor enim thesauri sunt in Christo sub uelamento sacramenti absconditi. In ipso enim est thesaurus omnis essencie, omnis sapiencie, omnis gracie, et omnis glorie.

66. Primo ergo in Christo Ihesu¹⁴ est thesaurus omnis essencie. Omnia enim que sunt, aut que fuerunt, uel¹⁵ que erunt, et¹⁶ que fieri possint,¹⁷ *ab ipso sunt*,¹⁸ *per ipsum sunt et in ipso sunt*.^b Cogita ergo, qualis est thesaurus iste, de quo *celum, terra, mare et omnia, que in eis sunt*,^c prodierunt. Unde de Christo¹⁹ dici potest²⁰ illud Matthei decimo tercio: *Qui profert de thesauro suo nova et uetera*.^d [f. 54v] Item²¹ illud Psalmi: *Qui profert*²² *uentos de thezauris suis*.^e

³ queque] *om. q*

⁴ rerum humanarum] *diuitiarum q*

⁵ corpore] *corr. ex q : corpus M*

⁶ Pater] *Deus Pater q*

⁷ uolens] *add. sacrificium M*

⁸ scilicet] *om. q*

⁹ consolari] *add. ex q : om. M*

¹⁰ aduentum] *add. Christi q*

¹¹ promittebat] *add. ei q*

¹² absconditos] *add. Isaie quadragesimo quinto q*

¹³ sunt in] *sub q*

¹⁴ Ihesu] *om. q*

¹⁵ uel] *om. q*

¹⁶ et] *vel q*

¹⁷ possunt] *potuerunt et possunt q*

¹⁸ sunt] *om. bis q*

¹⁹ Christo] *fort. ipso M*

²⁰ dici potest] *potest dici q*

²¹ Item] *add. uel iuxta sup. l. M : et q*

²² profert] *producit ut Vulg. M*

^a Tibi... absconditos] *Is. 45, 3*

^b ab ipso... in ipso sunt] *Rom. 11, 36*

^c celum... sunt] *Ps. 145, 6*

^d Qui... uetera] *Matth. 13, 52*

^e Qui... suis] *Ps. 134, 7 (LXX)*

67. Secundo,²³ <in Christo> est thesaurus omnis sapientie. Ipse enim cognoscit omnia, quecumque sunt, quecumque fuerunt,²⁴ quecumque fieri²⁵ potuerunt et possunt. Et non solum cognoscit res, sed etiam condiciones quas res habent uel habere possunt. Ipse enim est Deus, 'cui omne cor patet et omnis uoluntas loquitur, et quem nullum latet secretum'.ⁱ Non solum²⁶ ipse perfectissime cognoscit omnia, sed omnia que <cognoscuntur>,²⁷ ipse cognoscere facit. Ipse enim est lux, que illuminat omne lumen et conseruat in suo uigore. Iohannis octavo: *Ego sum lux mundi*.^f Item²⁸ de hoc thesauro <dicitur>²⁹ ad Colossenses: *In ipso*³⁰ *sunt omnes thesauri sapientie et scientie Dei absconditi*.^g

68. Tercio, est in Christo thesaurus omnis gratie. Ipse enim est *plenus gracia et ueritate*,^h de cuius plenitudine hauriunt angeli et homines. Ipse habet fontalem plenitudinem, *qui aperit manum suam et implet omne animal*³¹ *benediccionem*.ⁱ Et iste thesaurus graciarius est absconditus sub uelamine³² sacramenti altaris; Matthaei decimo tercio: *Simile est regnum celorum thesauro abscondito in agro*.^{33j} Quid hic significatur³⁴ per agrum nisi corporis Christi sacramentum, quod et de agro colligitur? In hoc agro habemus thesaurum absconditum, quia ibi latent omnia genera graciarius; *quem qui inuenit, pre gaudio illius uendit uniuersa*³⁵ *que habet, et emit agrum illum*;^k quia qui cognoscit huius

²³ Secundo in Christo] *add.* in Christo *M*

²⁴ fuerunt] *add.* quaecumque erunt *M*

²⁵ potuerunt et] *om.* *q*

²⁶ solum... cognoscit] solum autem res perfectissime ipse cognoscit *M*

²⁷ cognoscuntur] *corr.* *ex q* : cognoscunt *M*

²⁸ Item] *om.* *q*

²⁹ dicitur] *add.* *ex q* : *om.* *M*

³⁰ ipso] quo *q*

³¹ animal] *add.* rationale *q*

³² uelamine] uelamento *q*

³³ agro] *add.* et cetera *q*

³⁴ hic significatur] significatur hic *q*

³⁵ uendit uniuersa] vadit et vendit omnia *q*

^f Ego... mundi] Ioh. 8, 12

^g In... absconditi] Col. 2, 3

^h plenus... ueritate] Ioh. 1, 14

ⁱ qui... benediccionem] cfr Ps. 144, 16

^j Simile... agro] Matth. 13, 44

^k quem... illum] Matth. 13, 44

ⁱ cui... secretum] *Corpus Orationum*, ed. Moeller, CCSL 160A:131, n. 1135.

sacramenti plenitudinem, libentissime intermittit omnem³⁶ aliam operationem, ut se libere exerceat circa huius sacramenti³⁷ deuotionem, quia scit ibi se haurire uite eterne possessionem, teste Domino Iohannis sexto: *Qui manducat meam carnem et bibit meum sanguinem habet uitam eternam.*¹

69. Quarto, est in Christo thesaurus omnis glorie. Quidquid enim glorie habent angeli et homines, quicumque saluandi sunt usque ad³⁸ diem iudicii, de ipso quasi de thesauro omnia hec³⁹ hauriunt que pertineant ad gloriam corporis siue ad salutem anime.⁴⁰ Ipse enim est, qui *ponit in thesauris suis abyssos*,^m id est inexplicabiles illius glorie terminos. Et propter hoc iubebat⁴¹ nos Dominus⁴² ad hunc thesaurum properare, cum dicebat⁴³ Matthaei sexto: *Thesaurizate uobis thesauros in celo.*ⁿ Ad hos thesauros sancti peruenire desiderant:⁴⁴ et cum ad eos pertingere nequeant nisi per mortem,⁴⁵ *quasi effodientes thesauros gaudent uehementer, cum inuenerint sepulcrum.*^{46o}

70. Thesaurus autem iste graciaram <est>⁴⁷ absconditus [f. 55r] sub uelamento <panis et uini>⁴⁸ propter quatuor rationes; et [p. 564] propter hoc dicitur: *Tibi dabo thesauros absconditos*:^p primo, propter fidei meritum; secundo, propter cruditatis attactum;⁴⁹ tercio, propter sensus nostri imperfectionem; quarto, propter exclusionem infidelium.

71. Primo ergo⁵⁰ absconditus est thesaurus iste propter meritum fidei. Magnum enim sibi meritum cumulat qui septem aduersarios for-

³⁶ omnem] *om. q*

³⁷ Sacramenti] *add. operationem vel q*

³⁸ ad] *in q*

³⁹ omnia hec] *om. q*

⁴⁰ que... ad gloriam] *sive pertineat ad stolam corporis, sive animae q*

⁴¹ iubebat... hunc] *iussit nos ad istum q*

⁴² dominus] *om. q*

⁴³ dicebat] *dicit q*

⁴⁴ peruenire desiderant] *uehementer desiderant peruenire q*

⁴⁵ nisi per mortem] *antepon. post pertingere q*

⁴⁶ sepulcrum] *add. Iob tertio q*

⁴⁷ est] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁴⁸ panis et uini] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁴⁹ attactum] *attractum ut vid. M*

⁵⁰ ergo absconditus] *absconsus q*

¹ Qui... eternam] Ioh. 6, 55

^m ponit... abyssos] Ps. 32, 7

ⁿ Thesaurizate... celo] Matth. 6, 20

^o quasi... sepulcrum] Iob 3, 21-22

^p Tibi... absconditos] Is. 45, 3

tissime credendo <ea que sunt Sacramenti superat>⁵¹ Isti aduersarii sunt quinque sensus, qui omnes sentiunt non ibi esse corpus Christi. Et ymaginacio similiter contraria est, que nullo modo ymaginari potest quod tam magnus homo, integer Christus, qui pependit in cruce, possit sub tam modica hostia abscondi. Contra enim omnem rationem est eciam, idem quod corpus simul et semel possit esse in diversis locis, sicut apparet in hoc sacramento, quod est perfectissime in celo, est perfectissime nichilominus in altari,⁵² et tamen⁵³ non plura, sed unum solum idemque corpus. Propter huiusmodi fidei meritum est corpus Christi uelatum. Gregorius: 'Fides non habet meritum, cui humana ratio prebit⁵⁴ experimentum',ⁱⁱ

72. Secundo autem uelatum est⁵⁵ propter cruditatis attactum.⁵⁶ Horror enim cruditatis posset multos arcere <ab hoc sacramento>,⁵⁷ si uiderent uiuum hominem comedi⁵⁸ et crudam carnem deuorari.⁵⁹ Et propter hoc sub figura illius et uelamento datum est hoc corpus, quod consuetum est manducari, uidelicet <sub accidentibus>⁶⁰ panis. Unde ipse Dominus se panem nostrum uocare dignatus est dicens:⁶¹ *Ego sum panis uiuus*,^q ut hoc⁶² comedendo ipsum⁶³ sub accidentibus <panis homo>⁶⁴ non haberet horrorem cruditatis.

73. Tercio uelatum hoc est corpus Christi propter sensus nostri imperfectionem. Si enim Christus⁶⁵ in gloria maiestatis⁶⁶ sue,

⁵¹ ea... superat] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁵² est... altari] cum nihilominus sit perfectissime cibus in ara *q*

⁵³ tamen] *om. q*

⁵⁴ prebit] *praebet q*

⁵⁵ est] *add. corpus Christi q*

⁵⁶ attactum] *attractum ut vid. M*

⁵⁷ ab hoc sacramento] *corr ex q : ad hoc sacramentum M*

⁵⁸ comedi] *comedere q*

⁵⁹ crudam carnem deuorari] *crudas carnes deuorare q*

⁶⁰ sub accidentibus] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁶¹ dicens] *add. Ioannis sexto q*

⁶² hoc] *om. q*

⁶³ ipsum] *add. Christum q*

⁶⁴ panis homo] *add. ex q : om. M*

⁶⁵ Christus] *om. q*

⁶⁶ maiestatis] *claritatis q*

^q Ego... uiuus] Ioh. 6, 51

ⁱⁱ Fides... experimentum] Gregorius I, *Homiliae in euangelia* 26.1; PL 76:1197C.

sicut⁶⁷ est, seipsum ostenderet nobis,⁶⁸ nullus mortalis tantam maiestatem et claritatem sustinere posset nec aspectum.⁶⁹ Sicut enim Moyses ex consorcio sermonis Domini tantum splendorem ac claritatem uultus sui conceperat,⁷⁰ quod oportebat eum uelare faciem suam⁷¹ cum loqueretur filiis Israel, eo quod non possint⁷² intendere in eum propter claritatem uultus eius,^r sic et hic Christus condescendens nostre infirmitati, superposuit uelamen⁷³ sue claritati.

74. Quarto uelatum est corpus Christi propter exclusionem infidelium. Ipse enim dixit, *Nolite sanctum dare canibus, et⁷⁴ margaritas ponere⁷⁵ ante porcos.*^s Quod uerbo dixit, hoc hic facto impleuit:⁷⁶ quia faciem suam in sacramento abscondit, et sic *canes et porcos*, id est omnes indignos, [f. 55v] a cognitione huius sacramenti exclusit.

75. *Confiteantur ergo Domino misericordie eius*, quia prefiguravit nobis suum nobilissimum⁷⁷ corpus sub figura thesauri celestis.

<VI.> *De figura manna siue mannatis*¹

76. Sexto prefigurauit nobis corpus suum sub figura manatis. Et hoc est quod hic dicitur,² *Dixit Dominus ad Moysen,*³ *Ego pluam uobis panes de celo; egredietur populus et colligat quae sufficiant per singulos dies. Quod cum audissent⁴ filii Israel, dixerunt ad inuicem: Mahu? quod significat: Quid est hoc? Appellauitque⁵ Israel nomen eius man.*^a De hoc

⁶⁷ sicut] *add.* ipse *q*

⁶⁸ nobis] *om.* *q*

⁶⁹ tantam... aspectum] tantam claritatem aspectus *q*

⁷⁰ tantum... conceperat] tantum splendorem conceperat et claritatem uultus sui *q*

⁷¹ suam] *om.* *q*

⁷² possint] potuissent *q*

⁷³ superposuit uelamen] uelamen superposuit *q*

⁷⁴ et] neque mittatis *q*

⁷⁵ ponere] vestras *q*

⁷⁶ hoc hic facto impleuit] facto adimpleuit *om.* *q*

⁷⁷ nobilissimum] *om.* *q*

¹ De... mannatis] *rub. M : om.* *q*

² dicitur] *add.* Exodi decimo sexto *q*

³ Moysen] *add.* Ecce *q*

⁴ audissent] uidissent *q*

^r Moyses... eius] cfr Ex. 34, 29

^s Nolite... porcos] Matth. 7, 6

^a Ego... man] Ex. 16, 4, 15, 31

cibo⁶ scriptum est⁷ Sapiencie <decimo> sexto:⁸ *Angelorum esca nutriuisti populum tuum, Domine,*⁹ *et preparatum*¹⁰ *panem de celo praestitisti eis sine labore, omne delectamentum in se habentem et omnis saporis suauitatem. Substanciam enim tuam et dulcedinem tuam, quam habebas*¹¹ *in filios, ostendebas: et deseruiens uniuscuiusque uoluntati, ad quod quisque uolebat, conuertebatur.*^b

77. Ecce, hic sub figura manatis describitur nobis corporis Christi sacramentum ut cibus genere nobilissimus, sapore suauius, continencia dignissimus, et efficacia mirabilissimus.

78. Primo ergo corpus Christi siue dominicum¹² est cibus in genere sue nobilissimus, quia a sanctissima Trinitate in clybano uteri uirginalis igne Spiritusⁱ sancti decoctus, et uirtute ipsius Trinitatis ille idem panis¹³ ex pane materiali est effectus. Et hoc est quod dicitur hic: *Paratum panem de celo praestitisti eis sine labore*: paratum quidem aliquando in utero Virginis,¹⁴ nunc autem residentem in celo et latentem [p. 565] sub sacramento. Est ergo nobilissimus, quia nobilissimam habet causam. Est nichilominus nobilissimus, quia nobilissimi, uidelicet Angeli, manducant illum¹⁵ panem sine furfure sacramenti, qui nobis peccatoribus datus est¹⁶ sub cortice uelamenti. Et propter hoc excitans nos gracia Spiritus sancti¹⁷ ad graciaram accionem proponit dicens: *Angelorum esca nutriuisti populum tuum.*

⁵ Appelavitque] *add. domus q*

⁶ de hoc cibo] *om. q*

⁷ est] *add. in libro q*

⁸ decimo sexto] *corr. ex q : om. M*

⁹ Domine] *om. q*

¹⁰ preparatum] *paratum q*

¹¹ habebas] *habes q*

¹² siue dominicum] *om. q*

¹³ panis] *om. q*

¹⁴ uirginis] *uirginali q*

¹⁵ manducant illum] *comedunt eum q*

¹⁶ datus est] *datur q*

¹⁷ gracia Spiritus sancti] *Spiritus sanctus q*

^b Angelorum... conuertebatur] Sap. 16, 20-21

ⁱ in clybano... sancti] cfr ANSELMUS LAUDUNENSIS, *Glossa super Iohannem* 6.35; ed. Andrée, CCCM 267:113; Thomas de Aquino, *Summa theologiae* 1a2ae, q. 102, art. 3, ad 12.

79. Secundo datum est¹⁸ corpus Christi sub figura mannatis et est in¹⁹ sapore suavissimus. Sapor enim huius panis attrahit desideria nobilium²⁰ angelorum non solum,²¹ sed etiam in hoc mundo odor licet tenuissimus²² excitat corda hominum ut in odore [f. 56r] eius²³ continue²⁴ ad brauium et ad plenitudinis eius cumulum²⁵ attrahit. Et hoc est quod dicebat beatus²⁶ Iohannes euangelista: 'Odor tuus in me concupiscentias suscitauit²⁷ eternas'.ⁱⁱ Et hoc est etiam quod dicitur hic de corpore Christi sub figura mannatis, quod habebat in se²⁸ *omne delectamentum et omnis saporis suauitatem*.

80. Tercio est iste cibus in continencia dignissimus. Continet enim totam sanctam²⁹ Trinitatem: et propter hoc dicitur etiam uas Trinitatis. Continet, dico, per presenciam et assistenciam non per circumscriptionem. Ipsa 'est enim intra omnia, non inclusa; extra omnia, non exclusa; supra omnia, non elata; infra omnia, non prostrata'.ⁱⁱⁱ Ibi enim est Filius per incarnationem, Pater et Spiritus sanctus cum eodem per indiuisibilem unius substancie communionem: et propter hoc dicitur ad Patrem, *Substanciam enim tuam et dulcedinem quam habebas ostendebas in filios*,^{30c} ac si dicet,³¹ O tu, Pater, substanciam

¹⁸ datum est] *om. q*

¹⁹ et est in] etiam est cibus *q*

²⁰ nobilium] millium *q*

²¹ non solum] *om. q*

²² odor hic tenuissimus] *om. q*

²³ eius] *add. curratur M*

²⁴ hominum... continue] nostra odor eius et quotidie *q*

²⁵ cumulum] *add. attrahit M*

²⁶ et... beatus] unde *q*

²⁷ in me... suscitauit] Domine, concupiscentias in me excitavit *q*

²⁸ in se] *om. q*

²⁹ sanctam] sanctissimam *q*

³⁰ quam... filios] quam in filios habebas *q*

³¹ dicet] diceret *q*

^c Substanciam... filios] cfr Sap. 16, 21

ⁱⁱ Odor... eterna] Cum falsa attributione Ioanni Evangelista, THOMAS CISTERCIENSIS, *Commentaria in Cantica canticorum* 3.2; PL 206:197D.

ⁱⁱⁱ est enim... non prostrata] BONAVENTURA, *Itinerarium mentis in Deum* 5.8; ed. Quaracchi, *Opera omnia*, 5:310 | est enim... exclusa] cfr ISIDORUS HISPALENSIS, *Sententiae* 1.2.3; PL 83:541A, et alii.

<tuam>,³² id est filium tuum. Totam enim substantiam suam dat Pater Filio, et dulcedinem tuam, id est Spiritum sanctum,³³ quam habebas ab eterno, ostendis presencialiter³⁴ in seculo illuminatis mentibus sub hoc sacramento.

81. Quarto est iste cibus sub figura mannatis in efficacia mirabilissimus. Et propter hoc dicitur hic,³⁵ *Deseruiens uniuscuiusque uoluntati, ad quod quisque uolebat, conuertebatur.*^d Secundum enim quantitatem bone uoluntatis et secundum magnitudinem uite et sanctitatis attingitur effectus utilitatis, sicut dicit³⁶ Bernardus: 'Quatenus in bonis Domini pedem fiducie fixeritis,³⁷ eatenus possidebitis'.^{38iv} Et hec est ratio quod sancti ad nobilissimos effectus huius sacramenti peruenerunt, quia in bonis eius altissime fiducie pedem fixerunt. Et propter hoc legitur de beata Clara, quod sic cernebat <Christum>³⁹ sub sacramento latentem sicut in dextera Patris sedentem, et propter hoc⁴⁰ quia altissimam ad Deum habuit⁴¹ fiduciam, ideo meruit audire sub sacramento existentis loquelam auribus carnalibus.^{42v}

82. Secundum ergo quod quilibet Christo⁴³ occurrit, secundum hoc eciam Christus cum muneribus gracie sue ei se exhibebit, utpote magnis magne gracie donum, mediocris medie, et paruis parue, et malis male dantur.⁴⁴ *Cum Sancto enim sanctus eris, et cum peruerso*

³² tuam] *add. ex q : om. M*

³³ sanctum] tuum *q*

³⁴ presencialiter] praesentem *q*

³⁵ hic] *add. quod q*

³⁶ dicit] *add. beatus q*

³⁷ fixeritis] fixeris *q*

³⁸ possidebitis] possidebis *q*

³⁹ cernebat Christum] Christum *supplevi* : cernebat *M* : timebat *q*

⁴⁰ propter hoc] *om. q*

⁴¹ habuit] habebat *q*

⁴² existentis... carnalibus] existentem carnalibus auribus loquentem *q*

⁴³ Christo] *add. sub hoc Sacramento q*

⁴⁴ gracie... parue] mediocribus mediocre, parvulis parvule, malis male *q*

^d deseruiens... conuertebatur] Sap. 16, 21

^{iv} Quatenus... fixeritis] BERNARDUS CLARAEVALLENSIS, *Sermones super Cantica Cantorum* 32.8; ed. Leclercq, 1:231; PL 183:950A

^v beata Clara] Cfr *Legenda sanctae Clarae virginis, tratta dal ms. 338 della Bibl. comunale di Assisi*, ed. F. Pennacchi (Assisi: Tip. Metastasio, 1910), 4.28, 3.22, pp. 40, 31. Et etiam in *Acta Sanctorum* II Aug. 12 (Antwerp: Plassche, 1735), 760E, 759D.

peruerteris;^e et propter hoc legitur [f. 56v] de hoc sacramento: *Quod ab igne exterminari non poterit,*⁴⁵ *ab exiguo solis radio calefactum tabescebat.*^{46f} Hoc⁴⁷ erat <materia mannatis>⁴⁸ quod ad calorem ignis indurabatur et ad calorem solis liquescebat, ad significandum quod qui accedit ad hoc sacramentum, habens in se ignem carnalis uoluptatis uel humane cupiditatis, meretur indurari; ad ignem enim hoc sacramentum indurabatur. Qui uero accedit habens in corde suo⁴⁹ calorem solis, id est feruorem caritatis, meretur liquefieri, id est, uehementioris caritatis igne purgari. Ad radium enim solis istud sacramentum liquescit,⁵⁰ id est, per effectum⁵¹ liquefacit animam, ut dicere possit:⁵² *Anima mea liquefacta est, ut dilectus locutus est.*^g Et sic impletur in hoc sacramento quod in figura dicitur⁵³ de mannate, quod *in omnia transfigurata omnium nutrici gracia*⁵⁴ *deseruebat ad uoluntatem eorum qui a Deo desiderati sunt.*^h

83. Sed quia⁵⁵ legitur, quod filii Israel non peruenerunt ad istum cibum,⁵⁶ nisi prius exierunt⁵⁷ Egyptum, transierunt⁵⁸ mare rubrum, intrauerunt in⁵⁹ desertum, dulcorauerunt [p. 566] amaram aquam per immissum lignum⁶⁰ ad significandum quod qui <uult>⁶¹ uenire ad nobilissimos effectus quos supra diximus per hoc sacramentum desiderat,⁶²

⁴⁵ poterit] poterat statim *q*

⁴⁶ tabescebat] *add.* id est, liquefiebat *q*

⁴⁷ Hoc] Haec enim *q*

⁴⁸ materia mannatis] *corr. ex q* : nisi mane *ut vid. M*

⁴⁹ in corde suo] *om. q*

⁵⁰]liquescit] liquifiebat *q*

⁵¹ effectum] affectum *q*

⁵² possit] *add.* illud Cantici *q*

⁵³ dicitur] dictum est *q*

⁵⁴ gracia] gratiae tuae *q*

⁵⁵ quia] *om. q*

⁵⁶ istum cibum] cibum mannatis *q*

⁵⁷ exierunt] exissent *q*

⁵⁸ transierunt] transissent *q*

⁵⁹ intrauerunt in] intrassent *q*

⁶⁰ dulcorauerunt... lignum] dulcorassent aquam per lignum immissum *q*

⁶¹ uult] *add. ex q* : *om. M*

⁶² per... desiderat] huius Sacramenti *q*

^e Cum sancto... peruerteris] cfr II Reg. 22, 27; Ps. 17, 27 (LXX)

^f Quod... tabescebat] Sap. 16, 27

^g Anima... locutus est] Cant. 5, 6

^h in omnia... desiderati sunt] Sap. 16, 25

debet quatuor facere. Debet enim exire tenebras⁶³ uiciorum; debet facere dignum penitencie fructum; debet contempnere omne terrenum; debet conuertere amaritudinem sue⁶⁴ crucis in oblectamentum.

84. Primo ergo debet exire⁵ tenebras uiciorum: et hoc est quod⁶⁶ filii Israel primo exierunt Egyptum, postea uenerunt ad istius⁶⁷ cibi gustum. Egyptus enim tenebre interpretatur.^{vi} Exeat ergo tenebras uiciorum qui festinat ad harum dulcedinem graciaram,⁶⁸ ut de eo possit dici illud Apostoli: *Fuistis⁶⁹ aliquando tenebre, nunc autem lux in Domino.*ⁱ

85. Secundo debet facere condignum⁷⁰ penitencie fructum: et hoc est⁷¹ quod filii Israel primo pertransierunt⁷² mare rubrum. Quid enim significatur per mare rubrum nisi amaritudo penitencie, in qua est *contricio magna uelud mare,*^j in quo mari submergatur rex Egypti cum exercitu suo, id est dyabolus cum omni conatu⁷³ suo?

86. Tercio debet deserere omne terrenum: et hoc est quod⁷⁴ filii Israel, antequam sumerent cibum istum, uenerunt in desertum, id est, deseruerunt omne terrenum. Et quia ista⁷⁵ tria sunt, per que quis⁷⁶ solet⁷⁷ alligari mundo, uidelicet amor possessionis, uoluptas carnis,

⁶³ tenebras] de tenebris *q*

⁶⁴ sue] *om. q*

⁶⁵ exire] deserere *q*

⁶⁶ quod] *add. dicitur q*

⁶⁷ istius] huius *q*

⁶⁸ dulcedinem graciaram] gratiarum dulcedinem *q*

⁶⁹ Fuistis] Eratis *q*

⁷⁰ condignum] dignum *q*

⁷¹ est] *add. quod dicitur q*

⁷² primo pertransierunt] post transierunt *q*

⁷³ conatu] ornatu *q*

⁷⁴ quod] *add. dicitur, quod q*

⁷⁵ ista] *om. q*

⁷⁶ quis] *om. q*

⁷⁷ solet] *add. homo q*

ⁱ Eratis... Domino] Eph. 5, 8

^j contricio... mare] Thren. 2, 13

^{vi} tenebre interpretatur] HIERONYMUS SRTIDONENSIS, *Liber interpretationis hebraicorum nominum* s.v. Aegyptus, ed. de Lagarde, CCSL 72:66; PL 23:890.

cupiditas honoris, iuxta illud⁷⁸ Iohannis:⁷⁹ *Quidquid*⁸⁰ *est in mundo, aut est concupiscencia carnis, aut concupiscencia oculorum, aut superbia uite.*^k Ideo dicebat Moyses: *Ibimus uiam trium dierum in [f. 57r] desertum.*^l Hoc significat⁸¹ quod per uiam unius diei deseritur amor possessionis: per uiam alterius diei⁸² deseritur uoluptas carnis; per uiam diei tercie deseritur cupiditas honoris.

87. Quarto debet⁸³ conuertere amaritudinem sue crucis in oblectamentum,⁸⁴ ut delectat⁸⁵ eum portacio sue crucis, quam necesse est portare eum qui uult animam⁸⁶ saluare. *Qui enim non accipit crucem suam, sicut dicit Dominus, et sequitur me, non est me dignus.*^m Si ergo uis amaritudinem crucis tue conuertere in oblectamentum dulcedinis, habeas⁸⁷ in corde tuo memoriam dominice passionis. 'Etenim non sentiet sua qui Christi uulnera intuebitur', dicit Bernardus.^{vii} Et hoc est quod legitur de filiis Israel, quod priusquam uenirent⁸⁸ ad cibum dulcissimum, uenerunt in Marath ad potum amarissimum, quem cum pre amaritudine bibere non possent. Iussit Dominus ut in eundem potum lignum, quod figurabat crucem, mitterent, et sic amaritudinem dulcorarent.ⁿ

88. *Confiteantur ergo Domino misericordie eius et mirabilia eius filiis hominum, quia saciauit animam inanem, et cetera.*⁸⁹

⁷⁸ illud] *add. prime q*

⁷⁹ Iohannis] *add. secundo q*

⁸⁰ Quidquid] *Omne, quod ut Vulg. q*

⁸¹ Hoc significat] *ad significandum q*

⁸² alterius diei] *diei alterius q*

⁸³ debet] *add. homo q*

⁸⁴ oblectamentum] *add. dulcedinis q*

⁸⁵ delectat] *uidelicet delectet q*

⁸⁶ animam] *add. suam q*

⁸⁷ habeas] *add. semper q*

⁸⁸ uenirent] *uenissent q*

⁸⁹ et cetera] *et animam esurientem satiavit bonis, sedentes in tenebris et umbra mortis, uinctos in mendicitate et ferro q*

^k Quidquid... uite] *cfr I Ioh. 2, 16*

^l Ibimus... desertum] *cfr Ex. 3, 18*

^m Qui enim... dignus] *Matth. 10, 38*

ⁿ uenerunt... dulcorarent] *cfr Ex. 15, 23-25*

^{vii} Etenim... intuebitur] *BERNARDUS CLARAEVALLENSIS, Sermones super Cantica Cantorum 61.8; ed. Leclercq 2:153; PL 183:1074B.*

89. Tu ergo si te⁹⁰ sentis inanem, quere tuam replecionem⁹¹ in hoc sacramento sub figura pinguedinis;⁹² si te sentis esurientem, quere tuam refeccionem in hoc sacramento⁹³ sub figura panis; si te sentis in tenebris sedentem,⁹⁴ quere tuam illuminacionem in hoc sacramento sub figura mellis; si te uides⁹⁵ in umbra mortis iacentem, quere tuam reconciliacionem in hoc sacramento sub figura agni paschalis; si te cognoscis egenum⁹⁶ et mendicantem, quere tuam ditacionem in hoc sacramento sub figura thesauri celestis; si te experiris ferreum cor habentem, quere tuam mollificacionem in hoc sacramento sub figura mannatis. Quod Christus⁹⁷ nobis prestare dignetur, qui cum Patre et Spiritu sancto uiuit et regnat in secula seculorum.⁹⁸ Amen.

90. Explicit gloriosus sermo de corpore Christi.⁹⁹

⁹⁰ Tu... te] Si ergo te *q*

⁹¹ replecionem] impletionem *q*

⁹² pinguedinis] adipis *q*

⁹³ in hoc sacramento] *om. q*

⁹⁴ in tenebris sedentem] caecutientem et sedentem in tenebris *q*

⁹⁵ uides] sentis *q*

⁹⁶ te conoscis egenum] egentem *q*

⁹⁷ Christus] Iesus Christus *leg. post* dignetur *q*

⁹⁸ qui... seculorum] beatissimae Mariae filius *q*

⁹⁹ gloriosus... Christi] *om. q*